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por
OSCAR IGNACIO BARRAGÁN VILLANUEVA

asesorado por
DR. ERICK NAGEL VEGA

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by
OSCAR IGNACIO BARRAGÁN VILLANUEVA

advisor
DR. ERICK NAGEL VEGA

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*A la memoria de “Juanito”,
abuelo, padre y amigo,
sin ti, esto no hubiera sido posible.*

*To the memory of “Juanito”,
grandpa, father and friend,
without you, this would not have been possible.*

Equipado con sus cinco sentidos,
el hombre explora el Universo que lo rodea
y llama a esa aventura Ciencia.

Equipped with his five senses,
man explores the Universe around him
and calls the adventure Science.

– Edwin P. Hubble –

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Resumen

Los planetas gigantes del sistema solar tienen sistemas de lunas regulares alrededor de ellos, observaciones sugieren que su formación está ligada a la creación del planeta mismo. Los planetas se forman a partir del material de discos circumestelares, que son producto del proceso de formación estelar. Protoplanetas gigantes embebidos en discos circumestelares forman un disco circumplanetario alrededor de ellos con el material que es acretado, de este material se deben de formar las lunas. Con el objetivo de estudiar este fenómeno en detalle, en este trabajo se realizan simulaciones hidrodinámicas tridimensionales de sistemas planetarios en formación utilizando el código `FARGO3D`. Se estudia la evolución de un protoplaneta tipo Júpiter embebido en un disco protoplanetario orbitando una estrella con una masa solar. Se investiga la formación del disco circumplanetario alrededor de este planeta. El disco circumplanetario se forma por material que cae verticalmente proveniente del disco circumestelar. El disco circumplanetario tiene una distribución de masa dada por $\Sigma_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-1.9}$ y $\rho_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-3}$. El disco es grueso, con una tasa de $h/r \approx 0.4$. Rota con un perfil sub-kepleriano, siguiendo una ley de potencia $\Omega_z \propto r^{-1.7}$. Tiene un tamaño de $1/3$ el radio de Hill. La masa dentro de este radio es $\sim 0.03m_p$. Se encontró que los discos circumplanetarios son estructuras gravitacionalmente muy estables. Esta estabilidad es dada por su dinámica, por encima de su termodinámica. Por lo cual, se espera que todos los discos circumplanetarios sean estables. Esto implicaría que no hay formación de lunas a partir de inestabilidades gravitacionales. Sin embargo, los discos circumplanetarios poseen una cantidad ideal de masa y momento angular para formar lunas, por lo cual son excelentes reservorios para formar satélites alrededor de planetas gigantes. Ya que son una consecuencia natural de la formación planetaria, esperamos que exoplanetas gigantes posean sistemas de lunas alrededor de ellos.

Abstract

Giant planets in the solar system have regular moons around them, observations suggest that their formation is linked with the host planet creation itself. Planets form from circumstellar disks material, this is product of the star forming process. Embedded giant protoplanets in circumstellar disks form a circumplanetary disk around them from the accreted circumstellar disk material, from this material moons should form. With the aim to study this phenomenon in detail, in this work, hydrodynamic three dimensional simulations of planetary systems in formation are performed using the `FARGO3D` code. The evolution of a Jupiter-like protoplanet embedded in a protoplanetary disk orbiting a solar mass star is studied. We investigate the formation of the circumplanetary disk around the protoplanet. The circumplanetary disk is formed by vertical inflow of material which comes from the circumstellar disk. The circumplanetary disk follows a mass distribution given by $\Sigma_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-1.9}$ and $\rho_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-3}$. We found a thick disk with an aspect ratio of $h/r \approx 0.4$. The disk rotates with a sub-keplerian profile, following a power law $\Omega_z \propto r^{-1.7}$. It has a size given by $1/3$ the Hill radius. The mass inside this radius is $\sim 0.03m_p$. Circumplanetary disks are gravitationally very stable structures. This stability is given by its dynamics, rather than its thermodynamics. Hence, we expect that all circumplanetary disks are stable. This would imply that there is no moon formation due to gravitational instabilities. Nevertheless, circumplanetary disks have an ideal quantity of mass and angular momentum to form moons, they are excellent reservoirs to form moons around giant planets. Since they are a natural consequence of planetary formation, we expect that giant exoplanets have moon systems around them.

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Acronyms

ALMA	Atacama Large Millimeter Array
BC	Boundary Condition
CPD	Circumplanetary disk
CSD	Circumstellar disk
EOS	Equation Of Estate
GPU	Graphical Processor Unit
HD	Hydrodynamics
HST	Hubble Space Telescope
IC	Initial Condition
MHD	Magnetohydrodynamics
MMsN	Minimum Mass sub Nebula
MMSN	Minimum Mass Solar Nebula
MRI	Magneto Rotational Instability
proplyd	Protoplanetary disk
SED	Spectral Energy Distribution

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The first reported detection of regular moons around a –giant– planet was made at the beginning of the XVII century by Galileo Galilei (an english version can be found in [Galilei, 1989](#)). He discovered the four great moons of Jupiter, nowadays called the Galilean moons. Thereafter, it was found that all giant planets in the solar system have this kind of natural satellites. The majority of these have prograde and near-circular orbits, and they lie in the equatorial plane of the planet. [Canup & Ward \(2006\)](#) found a mass scaling for satellite systems around the giant planets of the solar system: all giant planets which contain Hydrogen (Jupiter, Saturn and Uranus) have a moon system with about 10^{-4} of their respective masses. These facts suggest that moon system formation around giant planets should be related to the planet evolution itself. Therefore, giant exoplanets too should have similar moon systems. [Bennett et al. \(2014\)](#) detected the first candidate for an exomoon around a giant exoplanet using the microlensing technique. Nevertheless, this discovery is uncertain. Since it is a free-floating exomoon-exoplanet system, it cannot be confirmed since it is not possible to observe this system again. They concluded that future experiments with microlensing could be sensitive enough to detect exomoons.

To understand moon formation around giant planets, it is necessary first, to understand the star formation scenario, and then the planet formation around a star. The following sections in this chapter are devoted to describe briefly and qualitatively the general scenario for stellar and planetary formation. We start by describing general aspects of circumstellar disks. We follow with the theories for planet formation inside these disks. We end with the role of the physical mechanisms which form a circumplanetary disk around a protoplanet. The last section of this chapter is devoted to describe the general aspects of this thesis.

1.1 Circumstellar Disks (CSDs)

It is well known that spiral galaxies –including the Milky Way– have cold regions where gas and molecules exist (this is called interstellar medium). The material from which stars and planets form lies inside these zones, in the so-called star forming regions ([McKee & Ostriker, 2007](#)). The two principal forces inside these regions are gas self-gravity and thermal pressure. As long as the

pressure balances the gravitational force, the gas stays in equilibrium. [Jeans \(1902\)](#) demonstrated that if a given region exceeds a critical mass, then it tends to collapse. This limit is called Jean’s Mass and varies as $M_{\text{Jeans}} \propto T^{1/3} \rho^{-1/2}$. Zones with a mass $M_* < M_{\text{Jeans}}$ remain static. If the same region gets colder or denser, its Jeans Mass becomes smaller and smaller until $M_* > M_{\text{Jeans}}$. This triggers cloud collapse, starting the star formation phase.

While the cloud collapses, its central region reaches higher densities by accreting surrounding material. At any given moment this region is very dense and it will start nuclear reactions, in this way becoming a star ([McKee & Ostriker, 2007](#)). While the central mass is evolving toward a star, far away from the protostar gas and dust are affected by the gravitational potential of the central object. In a general way, gas motion has two possibilities: it can be accreted by the star or, if it has enough angular momentum, it can balance the gravitational force and orbit the protostar. This brings as a consequence the formation of a disk around the protostar ([Terebey et al., 1984](#); [Shu et al., 1987](#)). These circumstellar disks (CSDs) are formed of gas and dust. As the disk evolves, planets are formed using this material reservoirs. For this reason these disks are also called protoplanetary disk or “proplyds” for short ¹ (e.g. [Lissauer, 1993](#)).

Disk formation via cloud collapse has been studied with positive results. [Yorke et al. \(1993\)](#) found that a collapsing cloud forms a central object which has a great portion of the initial mass (to form the star), while the rest of the material is kept around the central object as a disk in equilibrium. The formation of such a disk lapses near 4×10^4 yrs. Recent studies have yielded the same general results about circumstellar disk formation (e.g. [Hueso & Guillot, 2005](#)). Circumstellar disk formation is therefore related with the star formation process. This is the accepted model to form this kind of structures.

1.1.1 Observational evidence

Circumstellar disk formation is predicted by physics and also has been confirmed by observations. Both spectroscopic and photometric observations have confirmed the existence of this kind of disks, principally in star forming regions such as Orion and Ophiuchus. The first evidence of circumstellar disks came from the Spectral Energy Distributions (SEDs) at the beginning of the eighties (see the review by [Williams & Cieza \(2011\)](#)). Such SEDs are characterized by the stellar flux which generally peaks at the optical spectrum, and an infrared excess due to thermal dust emission in the disk. Nowadays it is possible to estimate disk properties from the infrared excess on SEDs of Young Stellar Objects (YSOs). Physical properties of circumstellar disks have been obtained from pure spectroscopic observations (e.g. [Nagel et al., 2010, 2013](#)).

The best circumstellar disk evidence is given by their silhouettes in star forming regions. Dust in disks absorbs background radiation, this generates an obscure region which contrasts with the bright stars (e.g. [O’dell & Wen, 1994](#); [McCaughrean et al., 1998](#)). A compilation of direct imaging taken with the *Hubble Space Telescope* (HST) is shown in figure 1.1.

1.1.2 Physical properties

Observational and theoretical work allows to yield physical properties of circumstellar disks. They have a dust-to-gas ratio similar to the Interstellar Medium (ISM) of 0.01 ([Draine, 2003](#)). This means that 99 percent of the disk mass is gas. However, although the dust is only the remaining one percent of the mass, it dominates the opacity of the disk. This opacity is used to estimate the amount of dust in a disk, by assuming a dust to mass ratio (e.g. [Beckwith et al., 1990](#)). The mean

¹The term protoplanetary disk and circumstellar disk refer to the same kind of object, a young star surrounded by a gaseous and dusty disk.

Figure 1.1: Circumstellar disk silhouettes in the Orion nebula taken with the HST. The bright background is generated by stellar radiation. Photons are absorbed by dust in circumstellar disks, revealing a disk structure around the bright protostar in the center of the disks. Image taken from <http://messier.seds.org/Pics/Jpg/m42prop4.jpg>

mass of circumstellar disks around a solar-like star is $\sim 5M_{\text{Jup}}$. A typical disk to stellar mass ratio is $M_{\text{d}}/M_{*} \approx 1\%$, for different stellar types (Andrews & Williams, 2005, 2007a).

The low M_{d}/M_{*} rate implies that disk self-gravity is not important for disk dynamics, hence disk rotation should be Keplerian. This has been confirmed observationally. Doppler broadening of CO lines –at millimeter wavelengths– coincides with a Keplerian rotation profile (e.g. Koerner, 1993; Mannings et al., 1997). This result is used to estimate stellar masses assuming a keplerian rotation of the disk (e.g. Simon et al., 2000).

The mass distribution inside these disks is given by a surface density profile which follows a power law $\Sigma \propto r^{-\alpha}$, where Σ is the surface density and α the power law exponent, with a canonical value of $\alpha = 1.5$ for a Minimum Mass Solar Nebula (MMSN), which is the minimum mass necessary to form the solar system (Weidenschilling, 1977; Hayashi, 1981). Values of α range between 0 and 1.5 (e.g. Mundy et al., 1996; Andrews & Williams, 2007b).

Typical disk radii lie in the range of 50 – 250AU. This range is estimated from silhouettes in star formation regions such as Orion and Opichius (e.g. Vicente & Alves, 2005; Hughes et al., 2008; Andrews et al., 2009). Estimations of disk height come from the hydrostatic equilibrium assumption, that the pressure and the component of gravity in the vertical direction are equal. Direct observations of silhouettes have shown that these disks are flared, which means that their height grows with the radius (e.g. Burrows et al., 1996; Smith et al., 2005). An analytic expression was obtained by Chiang & Goldreich (1997). They found that $h \propto r^{\beta}$, with $\beta \approx 1.3 - 1.5$, where h is the scale height.

Statistical studies of circumstellar disks in star forming regions have been used to estimate disk lifetimes. They range between $< 1\text{Myr}$ and 10Myr with a median of 3Myr (Haisch et al., 2001; Mamajek et al., 2009). Therefore, all physical processes inside these disks (including planetary formation) should occur in timescales contained within these values.

Figure 1.2: Image of HL Tauri taken with *ALMA* at millimeter wavelengths. The image shows the dust thermal emission. The darker zones correspond to the gap regions. Some of these gaps could be created by planets in formation. Image taken from http://apod.nasa.gov/apod/image/1411/HLtauri_alma_1800.jpg.

1.2 Planetary Formation

The idea that planetary systems such as the solar one were formed from the collapse of a cloud has been widely studied. [Safronov \(1967\)](#) demonstrated that the solar system could have formed from a protoplanetary cloud, where planets were created around a solar-like star from a protoplanetary disk with a mass $\approx 0.05M_{\odot}$. This disk-to-stellar mass ratio obtained theoretically is similar to those found later by observations (e.g. [Andrews & Williams, 2005, 2007a](#)). It has been estimated that inside circumstellar disks there is enough material to create planetary systems ([Beckwith et al., 1990](#)). Therefore planetary formation theories start with a protoplanetary disk.

The evidence of planetary formation inside circumstellar disks was first inferred from spectroscopic observations at millimeter wavelengths from the so-called pretransitional disks. A lack of emission at the mid-infrared suggests the existence of gaps in circumstellar disks (e.g. [Espaillat et al., 2007, 2010](#)). These gaps could be created by photoevaporation, magneto rotational instabilities (MRI) or gap opening by a companion (see [Williams & Cieza, 2011](#)). [Kim et al. \(2013\)](#) analyzed a circumplanetary disk survey in the Orion A region. They concluded that inner gaps are principally formed by opening by a companion, while photoevaporation plays an important role in external disk regions and MRI in just a few cases. The new image from the *Atacama Large Millimeter Array* (ALMA) of HL Tauri shows a clear example of what could be a planetary system in formation. It shows gaps at different radii suggesting the presence of protoplanets. This image is shown in figure 1.2.

Since the first detection of an exoplanet around a Sun-like star ([Mayor & Queloz, 1995](#)), almost

2000 exoplanets and more than 450 planetary systems have been discovered². This suggests that planetary systems are a common characteristic around stars. A really interesting phenomenon is the physical mechanisms which can create planets using circumstellar disk material. There are two mechanisms that could create planets, fragmentation by gravitational instabilities and *core accretion*.

1.2.1 Fragmentation by gravitational instabilities

The stability of a disk has been quantified by Toomre (1964) using the Q parameter. The basic idea is that if a disk region has a value Q greater than 1, that zone will be stable. Otherwise it will be unstable and that region will tend to collapse.

Mayer et al. (2002) found via N -body simulations that planets coagulate in cold regions of disks due to gravitational instabilities. These circumstances are reached far away from the star, where planets of the order of several Jupiter masses form. They did not find planet formation near the star, nor low mass planets. This result is not able to explain the majority of detected exoplanets. However, it is adequate to explain Jupiter-like planets in far orbits (also called wide orbits) around their stars, as the ones detected by Kalas et al. (2008) and Marois et al. (2008).

1.2.2 Core Accretion Model

The basic idea of the core accretion model is the accumulation of material around an initial solid core. This increments its mass over time due to accretion of the surrounding gas and dust. This mechanism can be divided into three principal steps (Bodenheimer & Pollack, 1986; Pollack et al., 1996). The first one is characterized by accretion of planetesimals, in this way a solid core of several terrestrial masses is formed. In the second step, planetesimal accretion continues, but at this time the accretion of the surrounding gas starts. This creates an envelope around the core that remains in hydrostatic equilibrium, forming a primitive atmosphere around a solid planet. This episode lasts around 10^6 years. The last phase starts at the moment when the solid and gas masses are comparable. This breaks the hydrostatic equilibrium, starting a runaway accretion which characterizes this third stage. This step determines the final mass of the planet and it is a relatively fast process which last $\approx 10^4$ years, forming planets of several times the mass of Jupiter ($1M_J = 1.899 \times 10^{30}$ g).

All this multiple evidence – from the “star-nurseries” in molecular clouds, dusty circumplanetary disks, gaps inside protoplanetary regions as HL Tauri, and multiple planetary systems detected in the last years – suggests a sequential physical scenario for planetary systems formation similar to the solar one. In this thesis this approach is assumed.

1.3 Circumplanetary Disks (CPDs)

Whatever way, the planets form and giant planet-moon systems – such as Jupiter and its Galilean moons – exist. They can be thought of as a “solar systems” in miniature, being Jupiter the central massive object and the moons the “planets” orbiting it. Naturally, the first idea to form a Jupiter-moon system is to assume a Minimum Mass sub Nebula (MMsN), with a formation similar to the MMSN. It also considers that a proto-Jupiter cloud collapses. In this scenario, the central region should form the planet, while a surrounding disk forms (called *spin-out* disk) similarly to a protoplanetary disk. This spin-out disk should have enough material from which moons could form (e.g. Lunine & Stevenson, 1982).

²from <http://exoplanet.eu/catalog/>, June 12, 2015.

Figure 1.3: Sequence of a circumplanetary disk formation, as was found by 2D simulations (e.g. Lubow et al., 1999; D’Angelo et al., 2002). (Left) At the beginning of star formation, a circumstellar disk is formed around the protostar. (Center) A protoplanet forms in the circumstellar disk, then it starts to open a gap in its orbit. (Right) When the planet is big enough ($\gtrsim 100M_{\oplus}$), a circumplanetary disk is formed around the protoplanet and is fed by circumstellar material.

Two-dimensional simulations have shown that gas accumulates around a protoplanet forming a disk-like structure, with material flowing from the protoplanetary disk via the L1 and L2 Lagrangian points (e.g. Lubow et al., 1999; D’Angelo et al., 2002). A schematic view of the formation sequence of the circumplanetary disk found by these simulations is shown in figure 1.3. Based on these results, Canup & Ward (2002) showed that the best model for a circumplanetary disk is a *gas-starved accretion* disk instead of a spin-out one. They emphasized the fact that the Lunine & Stevenson (1982) model has several weaknesses: deficiencies in accretion times of satellites, disk temperatures too high for ices in Ganymede and Callisto regions, etc. They demonstrated that the formation of the Galilean satellites from a gas-starved accretion disk is strongly favored over the formation from a gas-rich MMsN. Similarities in the growth processes assumed for Jupiter and Saturn, as well as in the features of their satellite systems, suggest that a common mode of origin produced the regular satellites of both planets (maybe ALL giant planets). Ward & Canup (2010) found later that at the planet formation phase a spin-out disk is formed first. During the formation stage, the spin-out disk switches to an accretion disk, reaching this last stage once the protoplanet has formed. Today, the term “circumplanetary disk” refers to the “gas-starved accretion disk” model by Canup & Ward (2002), from which moons should form.

1.3.1 Observational evidence

Circumplanetary disks are harder to observe than circumstellar ones, they are smaller and should be fainter than protoplanetary disks.

Greaves et al. (2008) claimed the first detection of a circumplanetary disk inside HL Tau. They used Very Large Array (VLA) observations at 1.3cm with a resolution of 0.06arcsec. These observations showed a compact feature in the disk at a distance of 65AU from the star, with an inferred mass of $\approx 14M_J$ ($1M_J = 1.899 \times 10^{30}g$). Subsequent observations of the same region did not agree with Greaves et al.. Kwon et al. (2011) did not find the dust thermal emission due to the circumplanetary disk found previously. Carrasco-González et al. (2009) suggested that the emission found by Greaves et al. can also be explained by free-free continuum instead of thermal dust emission. The detection of a circumplanetary disk in HL Tau is therefore not confirmed. However this questions the circumplanetary disk detection.

More recent works have shown better results in the search of circumplanetary disks. Using Karl G. Jansky Very Large Array observations at 7mm continuum emission, it has been estimated a massive planet ($> 5M_J$) around LkCa 15, with a circumplanetary disk less massive than $0.1M_J$, or

Figure 1.4: Image of FW Tau taken with *ALMA*. The color map corresponds to a mid-infrared image in the K' band. Isocontours denote the *ALMA* 1.3mm continuum emission, they are superposed to the stellar companion in the K' band, indicating the existence of dust. Image taken from [Kraus et al. \(2015\)](#).

smaller than 0.4 Hill radius ([Isella et al., 2014](#)).

[Osorio et al. \(2014\)](#) found a compact source which falls in the middle part of the outer annular gap of HD 169142. They argue that such emission can trace circumplanetary dust emission associated with the planet which created the gap. This could be tested in the next years via proper-motion measurements of such emission.

Maybe the best evidence for a circumplanetary disk is the *ALMA* image of the binary system FW Tau by [Kraus et al. \(2014, 2015\)](#). They resolved – via 1.3mm continuum emission – a stellar companion with a dust mass of 1 – 2 Earth masses. This object could be a circumplanetary disk with enough mass to form Galilean moons around a giant planet. The circumplanetary disk image is shown in figure 1.4. The color map corresponds to an infrared image obtained by [Kraus et al. \(2014\)](#). Solid isocontours represent the dust emission detected with the *ALMA* 1.3mm observation, suggesting the existence of a dusty circumplanetary disk.

This evidence suggests that a better detection of circumplanetary disk will be possible in the next years. This will help with their characterization, in order to compare with models.

1.3.2 Physical properties

As was discussed, recent circumplanetary disk observations are focused on detection. however their physical properties have not been obtained from observations. Instead of this, they are predicted via theoretical or numerical models.

Not all planets always form a circumplanetary disk. It has been shown, via simulations, that the existence of circumplanetary disks depends on the equation of state chosen for low mass planets. For isothermal and adiabatic simulations, this dependence cuts off above $100M_{\oplus}$ ($1M_{\oplus} = 5.97 \times 10^{27}g$ or $3.15 \times 10^{-3}M_J$), when gravitational effects are stronger than thermal ones ([Ayliffe & Bate, 2009a](#)). Whether planet with masses $\lesssim 100M_{\oplus}$ form a circumplanetary disk depends on the model. In the

majority of the cases, they only form spherical envelopes around them (Ayliffe & Bate, 2009a). Therefore circumplanetary disks are present only around massive planets ($\gtrsim 100M_{\oplus}$) (Ayliffe & Bate, 2009a,b; Machida, 2009).

Circumplanetary disks are gravitationally affected like a three-body problem of a test-mass influenced by two massive objects. It can be found theoretically that a gravitationally dominated region by the planet exists around it (this region is called Hill sphere), as well as Lagrangian points which characterize the system (a good introduction to the 3 bodies problem is given by Valtonen & Karttunen, 2006). It is natural to think that circumplanetary disks form inside the Hill sphere, since it is the gravitational domain region of the planet. A simple model developed by Quillen & Trilling (1998) shows that the typical circumplanetary disk size should be near $r_{\text{Hill}}/3$, where r_{Hill} is the Hill radius. This has been confirmed via simulations by Ayliffe & Bate (2009a) and Machida (2009). The first circumplanetary disks observations also agree with this value (Isella et al., 2014).

It has been estimated that circumplanetary disks are thicker than circumstellar ones. They have typical aspect ratios in the range $h/r = 0.3-0.6$ (e.g. Ayliffe & Bate, 2009a; Shabram & Boley, 2013). Ayliffe & Bate (2009a) estimated via simulations that the surface density of circumplanetary disks drops faster than for circumstellar ones, with $\rho_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-3/2} - r^{-2}$, and their temperature profiles have the form $T_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-7/10}$. Tanigawa et al. (2012) found a similar behavior, with $\rho_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-3}$ and $\Sigma_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-3/2}$. This result implies that circumplanetary disks reach a quasi-static hydrostatic equilibrium.

These values are not definitive, because they are model-dependent. However, these preliminary results about circumplanetary disk can be used for comparative purposes.

Circumplanetary disks are a relatively new subject in astrophysics. In the upcoming years, new and better models and observations will bring an improved understanding of these topics.

1.4 Objectives of this work

Moon formation around giant planets is a new and still open question in astrophysics. Latest studies suggest that circumplanetary disks are the ideal places to form moons around giant planets (e.g. Canup & Ward, 2002). It is well known that planets form in circumstellar disks via grain agglomeration and gravitational collapses (Mayer et al., 2002). But, how do moons form inside these disks? First simple models yield that grain growth is a mechanism which could form moons in circumplanetary disks (e.g. Canup & Ward, 2002; Tanigawa et al., 2012). Can moons be formed by gravitational collapses in circumplanetary disks? This thesis solves this question.

This result will help to understand the moon formation processes in circumplanetary disk. If gravitational instabilities are present, it would be a new branch in moon formation around giant planet theories. If they are not, moons can only be created by grain agglomeration, this could mark a break up between planet and moon formation theories.

In this work we are interested in studying the role of circumplanetary disk stability in the process of moon system formation. Our main objective is:

To study the stability in circumplanetary disks. If there are gravitational instabilities present, they could help in the moon formation process. If they do not exist, then other mechanisms are necessary to create moons around giant protoplanets.

We will concentrate ourselves in study a system formed by an embedded Jupiter-like protoplanet in a circumstellar disk, orbiting a Sun-like star. A circumplanetary disk should form around the protoplanet. We will model this via hydrodynamic simulations using the FARGO3D code. The specific

goals to reach are:

1. To read state of the art literature about circumstellar and circumplanetary disks , in order to identify the main aspects of them.
2. To analyze circumstellar disk models and to understand the different physical mechanisms which shape them.
3. To learn how to use the `FARGO3D` code by reading the manual, in order to know how to create a setup and perform the data analysis.
4. To generate the setup of an embedded Jupiter-like protoplanet in a MMSN around a Sun-like star. This setup should run in parallel with CPUs and GPUs, due to the high time-consuming simulations.
5. To analyze the data, to compare our results with other works, in order to validate our model. Then to obtain conclusions based in our objective.

1.4.1 Contents

This thesis is divided as follows:

1. This chapter is devoted to introduce the reader to the context of the planetary formation in circumstellar disks. We describe briefly the observational evidence and characteristics of circumstellar disks. This is followed by a discussion of the possible processes which could form planets in these disks. The observational evidence shows that circumstellar disks and exoplanets are common in the galaxy, therefore planetary formation maybe is very common. We finish this chapter with a brief description of the state of the art in circumplanetary disks topics: starting with a discussion about the possible existence of circumplanetary disks around giant protoplanets; then, the actual status of the observational evidence, and the latest results obtained from theoretical and numerical models.
2. Chapter 2 is a brief description of several circumstellar disks models. We start with a basic model – a vertical isothermal disk – to understand the fundamental physics which rule circumstellar disks. We continue with a brief discussion of more complicated models, adding more physics, such as: viscosity, heating, magnetic fields and gravitational perturbations. We present only the equations to solve (without derive them) for those disks and their physical implications. This chapter finishes with a justification of the use of simulations as a reliable tool to model a circumstellar disk – and other physical – systems.
3. The numerical issues of this work are described in chapter 3. A brief introduction of the `FARGO3D` code is given, describing its principal characteristics. We continue by describing the main algorithms used in the new `fargo_tools` package, such as: how `FARGO3D` files are read, coordinates transformation, the data transformation from binary to csv, parallelization, etc. We finish with a brief discussion of the files created to run our simulation in `FARGO3D`. The readers not interested in the numerical technical details can skip this chapter without loss of continuity.
4. Chapter 4 is devoted to describe the simulated physical environment. We start by describing the initial conditions, the circumstellar disk and the embedded planet models. Then the boundary conditions are explained, describing the previously defined and the new developed

boundary conditions in our simulations. We continue with a description of the simulated models (7 different models); they have the same physical configuration, but with different resolution and domain. This chapter ends with a description of the hardware used.

5. Results and discussions are shown in chapter 5. A study of the global evolution of the circumstellar disk is made, in order to validate our simulation setup, we compare it with previous works about circumstellar disks with embedded protoplanets. We continue with an analysis of the fluxes around the protoplanet. We make 2D and 3D analysis to characterize how the circumplanetary disk is formed. We follow with an analysis of the circumplanetary disk physical parameters, such as: density distribution, thickness, angular velocity, size and mass. We compare our results with previous works. An exhaustive analysis of the Q parameter is developed in order to characterize possible gravitational instabilities in the circumplanetary disk. We finish this chapter with a discussion of the implications of our results to create moon systems from circumplanetary disks.
6. Chapter 6 summarizes the main results and conclusions of this work.
- A. Appendix A is a manual to introduce the `fargo_tools` package to potential users. The process for downloading the package is described. We explain how to obtain `FARGO3D` outputs in order to analyze them with our tools, and how to use these tools with practical examples. We also describe how to visualize the data with the Paraview software.

1.4.2 What does this work provide?

To finish this chapter, let us summarize the main contributions of this work. They are:

- New and versatile tool to analyze the `FARGO3D` output files.
- The first circumplanetary disk simulations with the `FARGO3D` code.
- A detailed analysis of the 3D fluxes around the protoplanet.
- Simulations with different resolutions to eliminate numerical effects.
- A radial profile of the Toomre parameter in a circumplanetary disk to study the role of gravitational instabilities in the formation of moons around Jupiter-like protoplanets.

CHAPTER 2

CIRCUMSTELLAR DISK MODELS

Following the canonical model, circumstellar disks are composed principally of gas and a little fraction of dust, with a typical gas-to-dust ratio of 100 (Draine, 2003). This means that their dynamics and structure can be obtained from pure hydrodynamic calculations. The following sections are devoted to explain how a disk structure can be obtained from hydrodynamic equations. We start from a basic but instructive model, followed by more complicated models. This chapter ends with a justification for using simulations for complicated hydrodynamic studies.

2.1 The simplest model: Isothermal disk

Dynamics of an ideal fluid are governed by Euler's equation (Landau & Lifshitz, 1959):

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \vec{\mathcal{F}}, \quad (2.1)$$

where ρ , p and \vec{v} are fluid density, pressure and velocity, respectively, and $\vec{\mathcal{F}}$ corresponds to external forces. Assuming that the external force comes from the gravity of a point central mass M_* , the components of equation (2.1) in cylindrical coordinates have the form

$$\frac{\partial v^R}{\partial t} + v^R \frac{\partial v^R}{\partial R} + v^\phi \frac{\partial v^R}{\partial \phi} + v^z \frac{\partial v^R}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dR} - \frac{GM_*}{(R^2 + z^2)^{3/2}} R + \frac{(v^\phi)^2}{(R^2 + z^2)^{1/2}}, \quad (2.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial v^\phi}{\partial t} + v^R \frac{\partial v^\phi}{\partial R} + v^\phi \frac{\partial v^\phi}{\partial \phi} + v^z \frac{\partial v^\phi}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{d\phi}, \quad (2.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial v^z}{\partial t} + v^R \frac{\partial v^z}{\partial R} + v^\phi \frac{\partial v^z}{\partial \phi} + v^z \frac{\partial v^z}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dz} - \frac{GM_*}{(R^2 + z^2)^{3/2}} z, \quad (2.4)$$

here R , θ , z are cylindrical radius, azimuth and height, respectively. The right hand side of equation (2.2) is the centrifugal force term, which arises from the coordinate transformation. In order to describe a circumstellar disk with these equations, it is necessary to fix constraints obtained from

observational evidence. It has been observed that these disks are dominated by azimuthal velocity. Radial and vertical velocities are negligible. Therefore it can be assumed that v^R and v^z vanish. Late stage disks follow $M_{\text{disk}} \ll M_*$. This means that gravitational potential is governed by the star, while the self-gravity of the disk is negligible. Observations of circumstellar disks silhouettes show that they are thin, so it can be assumed that $z \ll R$. Taking these considerations in mind, the equations which govern the circumstellar disk dynamics are (Armitage, 2013)

$$\frac{(v^\phi)^2}{R} = \frac{GM_*}{R^2} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dR}, \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dz} = -\frac{GM_*}{(R^2 + z^2)^{3/2}} z. \quad (2.6)$$

2.1.1 Velocity profile

Equation (2.5) expresses the fact that gas rotates with a keplerian velocity plus a modification by pressure gradients in the radial direction

$$v^\phi = \sqrt{v_k^2 + \frac{R}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dR}}, \quad (2.7)$$

where

$$v_k = \sqrt{\frac{GM_*}{R}} = \Omega R \quad (2.8)$$

is the typical keplerian velocity and $\Omega = (GM_*/R^3)^{1/2}$ is the angular velocity. Armitage (2013) showed that for typical values of a thin disk, gas velocity relates with the keplerian one as

$$v^\phi \simeq 0.996 v_k. \quad (2.9)$$

For instance, radial equilibrium for a thin disk can be obtained from a pure keplerian rotating profile.

2.1.2 Vertical structure

Vertical equilibrium is given by equation (2.6). The solution of this equation depends on the equation of state. An instructive case is a vertical isothermal gas. Its pressure is given by

$$p = \rho c_s^2(R), \quad (2.10)$$

where c_s is the sound speed. In this case we assume it is just a function of R . Substituting equation (2.10) in (2.6), the equation to solve has the form

$$\frac{d\rho}{\rho} = -\frac{GM_* z}{c_s^2 (R^2 + z^2)^{3/2}}. \quad (2.11)$$

Its straightforward solution is

$$\ln \rho = \frac{GM_*}{c_s^2 (R^2 + z^2)^{1/2}} + \mathcal{C} \quad (2.12)$$

where the constant \mathcal{C} plays the role of a mid-plane density. Equation (2.12) takes the form

$$\rho(R, z) = \rho_0(R) \exp\left(-\frac{GM_*}{c_s^2(R^2 + z^2)^{1/2}}\right). \quad (2.13)$$

This is the more general expression for a 3D-density profile, where $\rho_0(R)$ contains the radial dependence. Following [Armitage \(2013\)](#), taking that the vertical component of the gravity is given by $\simeq \Omega^2 z$ and assuming a thin disk, $R \ll z$, equation (2.13) can be rewritten as

$$\rho(R, z) = \rho_0(R) \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{2h^2}\right), \quad (2.14)$$

where

$$h \equiv c_s/\Omega \quad (2.15)$$

is the disk scale-height. Analyzing equation (2.14), the physical importance of h is the break point where the density decreases dramatically as z grows. Therefore the ratio h/R , called aspect ratio, tracks the shape of the disk.

2.1.3 3D-density profile

Observations provide a surface density profile which has the general form (e.g. [Mundy et al., 1996](#); [Andrews & Williams, 2007b](#))

$$\Sigma(R) = \Sigma_0 \left(\frac{R}{R_0}\right)^{-\alpha}, \quad (2.16)$$

where Σ_0 is the mid-plane density at R_0 and α is the power law exponent which characterizes the CSD. This surface density obtained from observations is the integration over the height of the 3D-density profile, so, the relation between $\Sigma(R)$ and $\rho(R)$ is given by

$$\Sigma(R) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \rho_0(R) \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{2h^2}\right) dz. \quad (2.17)$$

The only part to be integrated is $\exp(-z^2/2h^2)$. It has the form of a gaussian integral, and its solution is

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{a^2}\right) = a\sqrt{\pi}. \quad (2.18)$$

Therefore the 2D-density profile is related with a 3D-density profile as

$$\rho_0(R) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{\Sigma(R)}{h}. \quad (2.19)$$

The general expression for an axisymmetric isothermal disk is then

$$\rho(R, z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{\Sigma_0}{h} \left(\frac{R}{R_0}\right)^{-\alpha} \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{2h^2}\right). \quad (2.20)$$

If we assume a constant aspect ratio $h/R \equiv H$, eq. (2.20) can be written as

$$\rho(R, z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{\Sigma_0}{HR} \left(\frac{R}{R_0}\right)^{-\alpha} \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{2H^2R^2}\right). \quad (2.21)$$

Hence a gas rotating with keplerian velocity and with a density profile given by equation (2.21) is enough to describe a thin disk supported by isothermal pressure around a dominant central mass. Figure 2.1 shows some plots which represent the density properties of this disk. The upper plot shows a cut in the $R - z$ plane of the disk density. The middle graph shows the radial profile of the density which is characterized by the α parameter in equation (2.21); a value of $\alpha = 1.5$ was chosen for this plot. The lower graph represents the vertical disk profile, given by the exponential part of eq. (2.21).

2.2 More complicated models

The model described in the last section is useful to understand the main mechanisms which shape a circumstellar disk. We have to keep in mind that this analysis was made assuming an ideal fluid modeled by Euler's equation and an isothermal equation of state. Realistic disks have viscosity, photoevaporation, magnetic fields, embedded protoplanets and more physical properties which change their shape and evolution. In this section some models are summarized to show the equations which have to be solved in order to reproduce more realistic circumstellar disks.

2.2.1 Viscous disks

We start with a viscous fluid. From equation (2.1), we can see that fluid dynamics are modified by external forces. Therefore, viscosity should affect the fluid dynamics the same way as an external force does. In the simple isothermal circumstellar disk case, this external force is the star gravity. Following Landau & Lifshitz (1959), an incompressible viscous fluid is described by the equation

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla p + \nu \nabla \cdot (\nabla \vec{v}) - \nabla \phi, \quad (2.22)$$

where the viscosity is determined by the kinematic viscosity coefficient ν . This viscosity coefficient depends on the physical mechanism which regulates the molecules interaction in the fluid. In the limit of a vanishing viscosity, $\nu \rightarrow 0$, we recover Euler's equation (2.1).

In order to introduce the kinematic viscosity in disks systems, Shakura & Sunyaev (1973) parametrized the kinematic viscosity with the disk parameters as

$$\nu = \alpha_\nu c_s h, \quad (2.23)$$

where α_ν is the so-called Shakura-Sunyaev parameter. The viscosity is implemented to disks using the α_ν parameter, together with disk properties (sound speed and scale height). Since viscosity acts like a force in the fluid equations, it modifies the material distribution. In fact, viscosity transports angular momentum in the disk. This can be quantified via the surface density evolution of a thin disk as (Armitage, 2013)

$$\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial t} = \frac{3}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[r^{1/2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (\nu \Sigma r^{1/2}) \right]. \quad (2.24)$$

Therefore the dynamic evolution of a circumstellar disk due to viscosity effects can be obtained solving eq. (2.24). This surface density profile evolution is a consequence of the angular momentum transportation. This equation has some analytic solutions for some ideal cases, such as the steady one ($\partial \Sigma / \partial t = 0$). In the most general case, temporal dependence have to be solved. Sometimes this can not be solved analytically, so, semi-analytic or numerical solutions have to be used.

Figure 2.1: Density profile of a thin disk. The upper figure shows the density values in the $R - z$ plane for a disk with $R_0 = 1$, $\Sigma_0 = 1$, $\alpha = 1.5$ and $H = 0.05$. Middle figure shows a cut at $\rho(R, z = 0)$, showing the decline of the mid-plane density given by the α parameter. The lower figure shows a cut at $\rho(R = 1, z)$, this figure reflects the aspect-ratio chosen $H = 0.05$ since that at $R = 1$, $z \approx 0.1$. Values are given in arbitrary units to show the behavior of the equations.

2.2.2 Heated disks

Since circumstellar disks form around stars, they are affected by the stellar radiation which generates changes in the disk structure and evolution.

If we consider a star emitting like a blackbody which heats the disk surface, it can be found that this generates a temperature profile $T_{\text{disk}} \propto r^{-3/4}$, which results in a sound speed profile of $c_s = r^{-3/8}$. This would imply that – from equation (2.15) – the aspect ratio varies as $h/r \propto r^{1/8}$ (Armitage, 2013). This result implies that the disk is *flared* (its thickness does not grow linearly for larger radii). A direct consequence of a flared disk is that these kind of disks absorb more radiation from the star, particularly in the outer regions, such that this would change the disk structure. Summarizing, if we take into account the stellar radiation would change disk morphology (principally disk thickness). There are more effects produced by the stellar radiation on circumstellar disks, such as photoevaporation. For more details see Armitage (2011).

2.2.3 Magnetized disks

Magnetic fields should modify the disk dynamics since disk particles interact with these fields. In the simplest way, it can be assumed that circumstellar disks are perfect conductors, therefore ideal magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) can be used for the analysis.

Following equation (2.1) magnetic fields should enter as force term which modify disk dynamics. The MHD equation to solve – including a potential gravity term ϕ – is (Armitage, 2013)

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t} + (\vec{v} \cdot \nabla) \vec{v} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \nabla \left(p + \frac{\vec{B} \cdot \vec{B}}{8\pi} \right) - \nabla \phi + \frac{1}{4\pi\rho} (\vec{B} \cdot \nabla) \vec{B}, \quad (2.25)$$

where \vec{B} is the magnetic field. We can see two new terms due to magnetic fields, the *magnetic pressure* given by $\vec{B} \cdot \vec{B}/8\pi$ and the *magnetic force* $1/4\pi\rho(\vec{B} \cdot \nabla)\vec{B}$.

Equation (2.25) describes the dynamics of a fluid affected by gravity and magnetic fields. It is also necessary to describe the magnetic field evolution to solve correctly the problem. Electromagnetic fields are described by Maxwell's equations (Jackson, 1999). In the ideal MHD limit, it is only necessary to solve just the homogeneous Maxwell equations: the magnetic induction equation (also called Faraday-Lenz)

$$\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\vec{v} \times \vec{B}), \quad (2.26)$$

which governs the magnetic fields evolution over time, and the magnetic divergence (Gauss law for magnetic field)

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{B} = 0, \quad (2.27)$$

to avoid non-physical magnetic monopoles. In the limit $\vec{B} \cdot \vec{B} \rightarrow 0$, equation (2.25) becomes Euler's equation, and we have a circumstellar disk as the one described in §2.1.

So, magnetic fields should modify the circumstellar disk equilibrium behavior due to the magnetic force term. Balbus & Hawley (1991) showed that a weakly magnetized disk – by a vertical magnetic field – presents a Magnetic Rotational Instability (MRI) which generates angular momentum transport in the CSD. The basic idea of this instability is the interaction between the magnetic field with the rotating system. This generates perturbations in the disk which generate turbulence in it. Magnetic turbulence also generates angular momentum transport, as we discuss in the viscous disk case (A detailed analysis can be found in Balbus & Hawley, 1998).

In general, the magnetic effects on a circumstellar disk can be parametrized via the α_ν coefficient like a viscosity effect in the disk as

$$\alpha_\nu = \left\langle \frac{\delta v_r \delta v_\phi}{c_s^2} - \frac{B_r B_\phi}{4\pi \rho c_s^2} \right\rangle, \quad (2.28)$$

where δv_r and δv_ϕ are the velocity fluctuation in the radial and azimuthal directions, respectively. The expression between the angle brackets denotes that the value is taken as an average over time. Some authors have studied the magnetic effects on the viscosity of circumstellar disks, like [Uribe et al. \(2013\)](#) and [Zhu & Stone \(2014\)](#).

If we discard the ideal MHD condition or if we consider more general magnetic configurations, equations become more complex and more equations have to be solved (this is briefly discussed in [Armitage, 2011](#)). On the other hand, these more general magnetic models could describe more realistic disks.

2.2.4 Gravitationally perturbed disks

In this subsection we will focus with more detail on which is the principal mechanism influencing a star with a circumstellar disk with an embedded protoplanet. [Artymowicz & Lubow \(1994\)](#) studied the interaction of a two-mass system with a gaseous disk. They found a general expression for a gaseous disk interacting with a binary system. In order to simplify the analysis, we will follow the analysis presented by [Kley & Nelson \(2012\)](#) for a planet orbiting a star. This simplifies the analysis by [Artymowicz & Lubow \(1994\)](#) as the mass of one of the two bodies is very small (planet) compared with the other (star).

Let us assume a circumstellar disk orbiting a star with keplerian rotation given by $\Omega(r) = \sqrt{GM_*/r^3}$, where M_* is the stellar mass and r the distance between the fluid element and the star. In this disk there is an embedded protoplanet with mass m_p , which orbits the star at a distance a_p in a circular orbit with an angular velocity $\Omega_p = \sqrt{GM_*/a_p^3}$. A fluid element feels the planet potential as

$$\psi_p(r, \phi, t) = -\frac{Gm_p}{|\vec{r}_p(t) - \vec{r}|}. \quad (2.29)$$

Let us notice that the planet position varies with time ($\vec{r}_p(t)$) because the planet is orbiting the star. We are assuming that the planet is rotating in a circular orbit and is periodic in azimuth since the orbit is closed. Then we can expand our equation (2.29) in Fourier series as

$$\psi_p(r, \phi, t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \psi_m(r) \cos \{m[\phi - \Omega_p t]\}. \quad (2.30)$$

The terms $\psi_m(r)$ are potential coefficients associated with each mode number m . These variables contain the planet mass information. Equations (2.29) and (2.30) are equivalent, they are just written in different bases. There are some advantages for using eq. (2.30): the radial dependence is given by the ψ_m functions, and the temporal dependence has been changed to a periodic function, from which we can obtain some conclusions.

Resonances will happen where the planet induces a strong response on the disk. This will occur when the fluid matches natural oscillations of the disk. From equation (2.30), ψ_p is stronger at $m(\Omega - \Omega_p) = 0$ and at the epicyclic frequency of the disk, $\pm\kappa(r)$ which is defined by

$$\kappa^2 = 4\Omega^2 + r \frac{d\Omega^2}{dr}. \quad (2.31)$$

Figure 2.2: Disk surface density and flow structure for a planet with mass ratio 9×10^{-5} ($30 M_{\oplus}$ for a solar-mass star) embedded in a constant surface density disk (normalized to unity). (a) The density structure 5 orbits after the planet’s insertion into the disk. Clearly visible are the spiral arms launched by the planet, the inner leading and the outer trailing. (b) Topology of the flow field, where the streamlines refer to the corotating frame. The disk split into an inner disk with circular streamlines (moving counterclockwise), a horseshoe-shaped corotating region (within the thick black lines), and another disk of circulating material (moving clockwise). Figure and caption were taken from [Kley & Nelson \(2012\)](#).

The resonance $\Omega(r) = \Omega_p$ is called *corotation* resonance, since the local disk angular velocity is equal to the planet. The other resonances are called *Lindblad* resonances, where $\Omega(r) = \Omega_p + \kappa(r)/m$ and $\Omega_p - \kappa(r)/m$ are the inner and outer Lindblad resonances, respectively. From equation (2.31) it is straightforward to show that for a keplerian disk $\kappa = \Omega$. Then the Lindblad resonance position can be calculated as

$$r_L = \left(\frac{m}{m \pm 1} \right)^{2/3} a_p. \quad (2.32)$$

Since torques are gravitational effects of the planet on the CSD, it is useful to compute the torques at these points. The torque along the disk is

$$\Gamma_{\text{tot}} = - \int_{\text{disk}} \Sigma (\vec{r} \times (-\nabla \psi_p)) df = \int_{\text{disk}} \Sigma \frac{\partial \psi_p}{\partial \phi} df, \quad (2.33)$$

where Σ and df are the surface density of the circumstellar disk and the surface element, respectively. The second equality of eq. (2.33) comes from the fact that the radial vector is perpendicular to the azimuthal motion. Calculating the torque at the Lindblad resonance position, the m th component is ([Goldreich & Tremaine, 1979](#))

$$\Gamma_m^L = \text{sign}(\Omega - \Omega_p) \frac{\pi^2 \Sigma}{3\Omega \Omega_p} \left(r \frac{d\psi_m}{dr} + \frac{2m^2(\Omega - \Omega_p)}{\Omega} \psi_m \right)^2. \quad (2.34)$$

These torques excite two spiral waves in the circumstellar disk (Goldreich & Tremaine, 1979). An example of these waves is shown in figure 2.2(a), the inner leading and the outer trailing waves are displayed. Density waves generate back effects on the planet: differences between inner and outer Lindblad torques generate a force which induces planet migration (more details about migration in Masset, 2008; Kley & Nelson, 2012).

The next step is to obtain the torque at the corotation resonance. For a simplified case, it has been estimated that the torque exerted by a low mass planet is (Kley & Nelson, 2012)

$$\Gamma_m^C = \frac{m\pi^2}{2} \frac{\psi_m}{rd\Omega/dr} \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{\Sigma}{B} \right), \quad (2.35)$$

where $B = \kappa^2/(4\Omega)$ is the second Oort constant. This torque influences on material corotating with the the planet, this forms a *horseshoe* region (Goldreich & Tremaine, 1979; Kley & Nelson, 2012). An example of this corotation zone is shown in figure 2.2(b).

Gravitational torques tend to push material far away from the planet due to angular momentum losses (or gains); such that this would start to open a *gap* around the planet. On the other hand, viscous effects tend to refill the gap. In order to open a gap for a planet, the gravitational torques should be greater than the viscous effects (Goldreich & Tremaine, 1980; Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994).

The viscous criterion for gap formation is given by (Lin & Papaloizou, 1993)

$$\frac{m_p}{M_*} \gtrsim \frac{40\nu}{a_p^2 \Omega_p}. \quad (2.36)$$

Theoretically –for an inviscid fluid– any planet could open a gap because $\nu = 0$. In reality, it is expected that disk have a mean viscosity of $\alpha_\nu = 10^{-2}$. therefore only giant planets open gaps in real disks.

Equation (2.36) only takes into account the gravity *vs* the viscous effects. Crida, Morbidelli, & Masset (2006) obtained a more general criterion for the formation of a gap. Taking into account thermal effects and disk thickness, the criterion is

$$\frac{3}{4} \frac{h}{r_{\text{Hill}}} + \frac{50\nu}{(m_p/M_*)a_p^2 \Omega_p} \lesssim 1 \quad (2.37)$$

The first left-side term refers to a thermal criterion, this requires that the planet’s Hill radius is larger than the disk thickness h , $r_{\text{Hill}} > h$ (Ward, 1997). The second left-side term arises from the competition between the viscous and the gravitational torques (Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994).

It is important to note that these effects (gravitational waves and gap opening by giant planets) appear as a natural consequence of the gravitational influence of a planet on a circumstellar disk. Therefore these characteristics should be clear signatures of planetary formation in CSD. Other effects (thermal, magnetic, etc.) should change particularities of this phenomena (such as gap width or depth), but they are not indispensable in order to study this kind of systems. A more detailed analysis of the interaction between a planet and a circumstellar disk is given by Masset (2008) and Kley & Nelson (2012).

2.2.5 Realistic disks

In previous subsections we studied briefly the general aspects of model modifications with respect to the one presented in section 2.1. We added more physical mechanisms, such as viscosity and magnetic fields. Real circumstellar disks should be affected by all these mechanisms, including others that we have not discussed here (e.g. chemical composition or photoevaporation). Hence,

circumstellar disks are very interesting objects with a lot of physical mechanisms which shape their evolution. There are several review articles for the interested reader with more circumstellar disk details (Williams & Cieza, 2011; Armitage, 2011; Kley & Nelson, 2012; Dullemond & Monnier, 2010; van Dishoeck, 2004; Zuckerman, 2001).

2.3 Simulations as a great approach to realistic disks

Analytic disk models are far away from realistic ones, as long as more physical mechanisms are added the solution becomes complicated. With the fast evolution in computer sciences, an alternative way to solve physical equations has been created. Simulations have become a great alternative to model disks (and a lot of physical systems). Computer simulations do not have the exact solutions of theoretical models, but it is possible to get much more complicated models, therefore the sacrifice is worth it. Nowadays to reach the state of the art of the new observational evidence, computer simulations are a great option.

It is necessary to keep in mind that the perfect simulation does not exist. It is impossible to create a simulation which contains all the physical mechanisms which govern the evolution of a real system. One limitation is due to computer time, as long as more physics are added, more equations have to be solved. This slows simulations even in the more powerful computers. This could change in the forthcoming years. A more important limitation is to restrict simulation parameters. If more physics are added more input parameters must be fixed or calculated. The fixed ones are obtained from observations or theoretical models but the others need to be computed from simulations. This becomes a problem for really complicated models, since it is not worth it to have a lot of free parameters.

Therefore it is always necessary to make assumptions in the model based on the physical mechanisms that we want to study. For example, we see that protoplanets effects on a circumstellar disk are a natural consequence of gravitational torques, then if we are interested in study this phenomenon, it is only necessary –as a first approximation– to solve the gravitational influence, in order to obtain conclusions about the system.

2.3.1 Simulations in astrophysics

Simulations are a growing branch in astrophysics, actually some people call this “Numerical Astrophysics”. They have been used to study different astrophysical phenomena, obtaining satisfactory results, for example: galactic interactions were studied via N-body simulations, obtaining results in agreement with observations (e.g. Toomre & Toomre, 1972). Simulations have also been useful to study complex physical mechanisms, such as black holes or relativistic particles (e.g. Font, 2003; Barragán & Jeyakumar, 2015). There have been also simulations which reproduce the actual large scale structure of the Universe (e.g. Vogelsberger et al., 2014). These examples show that numerical simulations are a reliable tool to study astrophysical issues.

Simulations have also been useful on the study of circumstellar disk physics: It has been shown that it is possible to create giant planets from collapse due to gravitational instabilities (e.g. Mayer et al., 2002), and also from accretion of grains (e.g. Pollack et al., 1996). It is possible that heated torques counteract the gravitational torques, this could explain the formation of giant planets near their stars (Benítez-Llambay et al., 2015). Canup & Ward (2002) based their model of circumplanetary disk formation from 2D simulations of a circumstellar disk by Lubow et al. (1999). The central subject of this work, circumplanetary disks, has been widely studied by computer simulations. This yields their possible morphology and properties (e.g. Ayliffe & Bate, 2009a; Machida, 2009; Tanigawa et al., 2012).

CHAPTER 3

NUMERICAL WORK

This chapter is devoted to explain the numerical generalities of this work. The first section presents a fast description of the FARGO3D code. The second part describes a group of subroutines that we called `fargo_tools` which were developed in order to analyze and visualize the output data. Finally, in the last section the new setup files in the FARGO3D code are described.

3.1 The FARGO3D code

Simulations in this work were made using the FARGO3D code, written by Pablo Benítez Llabay and Frédéric Masset, which is a generalization of a previous 2D version named FARGO (Masset, 2000). The code has been written for Unix base systems and is well documented in its official web site (<http://fargo.in2p3.fr/>). This 3D code has been used in a great variety of studies as well as the 2D version (e.g. Regály et al., 2012; Lega et al., 2014; Benítez-Llabay et al., 2015; Álvarez et al., 2015).

It solves the hydrodynamics (continuity, Navier-Stokes and energy) and magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) equations on an eulerian grid by using the finite differences method. This code is suited specially to model disk systems, such as the circumstellar ones. It uses a modification in the azimuthal transport equation that allows speed up approximately a factor of ten compared to a pure advection case (Masset, 2000). FARGO stands by “Fast Advection Rotating Objects”, therefore this code is the best option to study this kind of systems.

Another advantage on using this code is its capability to run in a parallel scheme, for robust computing simulations, both in multiple cores (via MPI) and multiple Graphical Processor Units or GPUs (using CUDA). This reduces the computational time in a considerable way, depending on user’s hardware capabilities.

To run this code, it is necessary to implement initial and boundary conditions of a given problem. After that the code can be executed. Some output files are generated, these contain field data at a given simulation time. The next section explains the numerical method developed to analyze FARGO3D outputs. The initial and boundary conditions used in this work are described in the next chapter.

3.2 The `fargo_tools` routines

The output files which contain the field data in `FARGO3D` are binary and unformatted arrays stored in the `output/SETUP` directory. `SETUP` is fixed by the user in the `.par` file (see `FARGO3D` manual). In order to analyze the output files generated by this code, a group of programs and routines were developed. A set of `FORTTRAN90` files called `fargo_tools` were written with the aim to put the original output binary files in a friendly way. These tools were developed from the template `reader.f90` inside the default `utils` directory in the root `FARGO3D` directory. These programs were created by Oscar Barragán, Francisco Rendón & Ramiro Álvarez. This package is available on https://github.com/oscaribv/fargo_tools as open source under the `GPLv3` license. A manual to use these routines can be found in the appendix A. The main directory is divided in different parts, where the most important one is the `sources.f90` directory. The next lines describe the content of these files.

3.2.1 Reading the files

In general, all tools work with the field data files generated by `FARGO3D`. These are the `gasdensm.dat`, `gasvxm.dat`, `gasvym.dat`, `gasvzm.dat` and `gasenergym.dat` archives, where m is an integer (the magnetic field is still not included). Each tool reads these files and produces a result.

Each field is stored in 1D-array of $NX \times NY \times NZ \times 8$ bytes, where NX , NY , NZ are the original grid sizes and 8 is due to the eight bytes values in each cell. In this way the data is stored in the RAM memory of the computer. This allows the numerical manipulation of the data.

3.2.2 Coordinates transformation: `trans_coords.f90`

To obtain useful 3D visualization of data, it is necessary to transform the output files in spherical or cylindrical coordinates to rectangular ones. It was created a file called `trans_coords.f90` where all these transformations are performed. Inside this file there are subroutines where data is transformed. The basic idea is to take the sizes and the arrays of the data in the original form. Inside these subroutines data is transformed and saved in csv files.

The program takes a cell point labeled by i, j and k that corresponds to a point x'_1, x'_2 and x'_3 , where the prime symbol corresponds to curvilinear coordinates. In the most general way, the transformation between curvilinear and rectangular coordinates is straightforward since there are canonical functions which relate them

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= x_1(x'_1, x'_2, x'_3), \\ x_2 &= x_2(x'_1, x'_2, x'_3), \\ x_3 &= x_3(x'_1, x'_2, x'_3). \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

Besides of the transformation of the coordinates, it is necessary to transform the fields. In order to do this, we follow the tensor transformation rules (see [Borisenko & Tarapov, 1979](#)). For zero-order tensor or scalars, the transformation has the easy form

$$a = a'. \tag{3.2}$$

First-order tensors (vectors) are transformed in a contravariant way by

$$v^m = \frac{dx^m}{dx^{n'}} v^{n'}. \tag{3.3}$$

To transform the field output files of FARGO3D, the equations (3.1), (3.2) and (3.3) must be used together. The transformation from cylindrical and spherical to rectangular coordinates are described in the next subsections.

Cylindrical to Rectangular

The rectangular coordinates are function of the cylindrical ones as

$$x = R \cos \phi, \quad (3.4)$$

$$y = R \sin \phi, \quad (3.5)$$

$$z = z, \quad (3.6)$$

where R is the radial cylindrical coordinate, ϕ azimuth and z the vertical direction. The transformation coefficients have the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dR} &= \cos \phi & \frac{dx}{d\phi} &= -R \sin \phi & \frac{dx}{dz} &= 0 \\ \frac{dy}{dR} &= \sin \phi & \frac{dy}{d\phi} &= R \cos \phi & \frac{dy}{dz} &= 0 \\ \frac{dz}{dR} &= 0 & \frac{dz}{d\phi} &= 0 & \frac{dz}{dz} &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

From equations (3.2), (3.3) and (3.7) the transformation rules for the fields from cylindrical to rectangular coordinates are

$$\rho = \rho^{\text{cyl}}, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\epsilon = \epsilon^{\text{cyl}}, \quad (3.9)$$

$$v^x = \cos \phi v^R - R \sin \phi v^\phi, \quad (3.10)$$

$$v^y = \sin \phi v^R + R \cos \phi v^\phi, \quad (3.11)$$

$$v^z = v^z, \quad (3.12)$$

for each i, j, k of the grid. Figure 3.1 shows a representation of the data cube before and after the coordinate transformation.

Spherical to Rectangular

The rectangular coordinates are function of the spherical ones as

$$x = r \sin \theta \cos \phi, \quad (3.13)$$

$$y = r \sin \theta \sin \phi, \quad (3.14)$$

$$z = r \cos \theta, \quad (3.15)$$

Figure 3.1: (Left) Orthogonal representation of the cube in cylindrical coordinates of the output file of FARGO3D. (Right) Grid representation of the cylindrical grid after applying the coordinate transformation.

where r is the radial spherical coordinate, ϕ azimuth and θ colatitude. The transformation coefficients have the form

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dr} &= \sin \theta \cos \phi & \frac{dx}{d\theta} &= r \cos \theta \cos \phi & \frac{dx}{d\phi} &= -r \sin \theta \sin \phi \\ \frac{dy}{dr} &= \sin \theta \sin \phi & \frac{dy}{d\theta} &= r \cos \theta \sin \phi & \frac{dy}{d\phi} &= r \sin \theta \cos \phi \\ \frac{dz}{dr} &= \cos \theta & \frac{dz}{d\theta} &= -r \sin \theta & \frac{dz}{d\phi} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

From equations (3.2),(3.3) and (3.16) the transformation rules from spherical to rectangular coordinates are

$$\rho = \rho^{\text{sph}}, \quad (3.17)$$

$$\epsilon = \epsilon^{\text{sph}}, \quad (3.18)$$

$$v^x = \sin \theta \cos \phi v^r + r \cos \theta \cos \phi v^\theta - r \sin \theta \sin \phi v^\phi, \quad (3.19)$$

$$v^y = \sin \theta \sin \phi v^r + r \cos \theta \sin \phi v^\theta + r \sin \theta \cos \phi v^\phi, \quad (3.20)$$

$$v^z = \cos \theta v^r - r \sin \theta v^\theta, \quad (3.21)$$

for each i, j, k of the grid. Figure 3.2 shows a representation of the data cube before and after the coordinate transformation.

3.2.3 Creating csv files: t2csv.f90

The principal motivation to create csv files comes from the fact that these files can be read by 3D visualization programs, such as Paraview (<http://www.paraview.org/>). This makes the data visualization and analysis of scalar and vector fields possible.

Figure 3.2: (Left) Orthogonal representation of the cube in spherical coordinates of the output file of FARGO3D. (Right) Grid representation of the spherical grid after applying the coordinate transformation.

This subroutine reads an input file, which specifies the grid sizes and domain, it is also defined which data files must be analyzed and the grid geometry. It reads the binary `.dat` files, after that it transforms the coordinates. It saves the transformed data with the name `disk m .dat` inside a directory named `csv_files`, where m corresponds to the `.dat` files.

The header of the `disk m .dat` is

```
X, Y, Z, lden, vx, vy, vz, lenergy,
```

where X , Y , Z establish the coordinates in rectangular coordinates, vx , vy , vz for the velocity components in the same coordinates and $lden$, $lenergy$ for the base ten logarithm of density and energy, respectively. Each row below this header corresponds to a point in the grid with its respective field values. These files can be used by multiple programs that allow csv files as input, in this work, the previous mentioned Paraview program is used.

3.2.4 Extract a part of the grid: `extracter.f90`

FARGO3D generates output binary files with sizes $NX \times NY \times NZ \times 8$ which contain all data of the simulations. For high-resolution simulations this becomes of the order of GigaBytes. This huge size makes the analysis of the data problematic. The `extracter.f90` file allows to obtain binary files with sizes $NX' \times NY' \times NZ' \times 8$. NX' is obtained from a minimum value $NX_{\min} < NX$ and a maximum $NX_{\max} < NX$. Both values are given by the user, therefore $NX' = NX_{\max} - NX_{\min}$ is the size in X of the new array (NY' and NZ' are obtained in a similar way).

This subroutine is useful in cases where a large region has been simulated, but the region of interest is just a small part of it. This allows that the zone of interest can be extracted, in order to obtain much smaller data files. These new smaller binary files can be transformed to csv files with `t2csv` and visualized with Paraview, this speed up the data analysis.

The special case where this subroutine is used is to extract the zone corresponding to the circumplanetary disk from a circumstellar disk simulation. This makes possible to analyze the circumplanetary data of a high-resolution simulation in a laptop.

3.2.5 Parallelization

For high resolution simulations, there are millions of points which need to be transformed by the previous described subroutines. This process can take several minutes to work with just a file. For runs with hundred of outputs, this can reach some days of data transformation. In order to avoid this problem, the previous described subroutines were parallelized using `OPENMP` to run in several CPUs at the same time.

The parallelization was not made with the aim to transform a file with multiple cores, instead of this, it was made with the objective to manipulate multiple files at the same time, each file with a different CPU. The parallelization is worthless if transformation is just for one file. But if the number of files to be transformed is greater than one, the parallelization will be effective. This parallelization allows a maximum speed up of the order of N in some cases, where N is the number of computer cores.

3.3 A new FARGO3D setup

In this work a new FARGO3D setup was developed in order to generate the simulation. It was created based on the FARGO3D User Guide Release 0.9. The generalities of this setup are described in next chapter. For the reader familiarized with FARGO3D, a new set of `.opt`, `.par`, `.bound`, `boundaries.txt` and `condinit.c` files were written. Additional to this, a new function `accretion.c` was developed to treat planet accretion, and some little modifications inside `allogas.c` and `main.c` were made to include `accretion.c`.

CHAPTER 4

SIMULATION SETUPS

To prescribe any simulation, some important parameters must be fixed. Initial and boundary conditions fix the system configuration where the physics work. Assumptions must be taken into account based on the objectives. At the same time, an appropriate domain and resolution have to be chosen in such a way that the physical mechanism to study is well described. On the other hand, these must be selected in a way to speed up the computational time.

In order to compare simulations in this work with the solar system – specifically with Jupiter – parameters were chosen to mimic a Minimum Mass Solar Nebula (MMSN), this is defined as the minimum mass required to form the solar system (Safronov, 1967; Hayashi, 1981).

Parameters to prescribe a circumstellar disk and a Jupiter-like protoplanet are described in the first section. The chosen boundary conditions are set in section 2. While section 3 is devoted to the domain and the resolution. The last section describes the hardware used in this work.

4.1 Initial Conditions (IC)

4.1.1 Scaling rules

Simulations are unitless, all parameters are scaled with the reference values. The unit mass is taken as the stellar mass M_* , the unit of length is the planet semi-major axis a_p , and the gravitational constant is taken equal to one ($G = 1$). From these assumptions, the angular velocity of the planet ($\Omega_p = \sqrt{GM_*/a_p^3}$) is unity, while the unit of time is the planet’s orbital period divided by 2π . For a solar mass star and a Jupiter-like protoplanet at a distance of 5.2AU, the time step is $11.68/2\pi \approx 1.89\text{yr}$. All simulations were ran in spherical coordinates. We follow the FARGO3D coordinate notation: the first coordinate is azimuth, the second one is spherical radius and the last one is colatitude. Therefore vectors have the form (ϕ, r, θ) , where ϕ , r and θ are azimuth, spherical radius and colatitude, respectively. Unitless fixed parameters are shown in table 4.1, a better description of these is given in next subsections.

	Parameter	Unitless value
Circumstellar disk	Σ_0	6×10^{-4}
	\vec{v}	$(v'_k, 0, 0)$
	α	1.5
	h/r	0.05
Planet	m_p	1×10^{-3}
	a_p	1
	e	0.0
	s (RocheSmoothing)	$1.5\Delta r$ ($1.5\Delta r/r_{\text{Hill}}$)
	$r_{\text{acc}} (\lambda)$	$1.5\Delta r$ ($1.5\Delta r/r_{\text{Hill}}$)
	f	1×10^{-4}

Table 4.1: Fixed parameters used in simulations. See text for a description of these parameters.

4.1.2 Circumstellar disk model

As initial condition a steady inviscid non-magnetized disk with an embedded Jupiter-like protoplanet was used. The circumstellar disk is a thin, pressure supported structure as the one described in §2.1. Equations (2.21) for the density profile and (2.8) for the velocity were fixed as the initial profile.

Parameters were chosen following Szulágyi et al. (2014), they also assumed a MMSN. In this canonical model the surface density, the surface density power law and the aspect ratio are $\Sigma_0 = 6 \times 10^{-4}$. $\alpha = 1.5$, and $H \equiv h/r = 0.05$, respectively (see equation (2.21)). In this unit system the Keplerian velocity is

$$v_k = r^{-1/2}. \quad (4.1)$$

Since the principal objective of this work is to study the fluxes and the circumplanetary disk around a protoplanet, a frame where the planet is at rest was adopted. This can be achieved if the system of reference is co-rotating with the planet. The orbital velocity of a fluid element in this co-rotating frame of reference is

$$v'_k = v_k - \Omega_p r, \quad (4.2)$$

where Ω_p is the planet angular velocity, equal to one in this units system. From equation (4.2), it can be inferred that the inner part of the circumstellar disk has a negative velocity and the outer part a positive one, while at the planet position, equation (4.2) is zero.

A vertical isothermal disk is simulated, hence the equation of state is

$$p = c_s^2 \rho. \quad (4.3)$$

From equation (2.15) the sound velocity is related to the disk parameters as

$$c_s = \frac{h}{r} v_k. \quad (4.4)$$

Since the aspect ratio h/r is assumed constant, the sound speed varies as $c_s \propto r^{-1/2}$. This profile is a first approximation for a disk heated by a central star (Armitage, 2013). The viscosity module of FARGO3D was disabled, hence the Shakura & Sunyaev (1973) viscosity parameter α_ν is not implemented.

4.1.3 Planet setup

The planet influence on the fluid is modeled as a force due to a point mass potential Ψ . While the planet accretion is modeled as a sink region at the planet position. The planet is located at $\phi_p = 0$, $r_p = a_p = 1$, $\theta_p = \pi/2$, where a_p is the semi-major axis. The eccentricity was fixed as $e = 0.0$ to force it to follow a circular orbit. Planet mass is $m_p = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ to mimic a Jupiter-like protoplanet. It does not feel the disk potential, hence there is no migration.

Planet potential

The gravitational influence of the planet on a fluid element, with coordinates (ϕ, r, θ) , is modeled with the potential

$$\Psi = -\frac{Gm_p}{\sqrt{\xi^2 + s^2}}, \quad (4.5)$$

where

$$\xi = \sqrt{r^2 + r_p^2 - 2rr_p [\sin \theta \sin \theta_p \cos(\phi - \phi_p) + \cos \theta \cos \theta_p]}, \quad (4.6)$$

is the distance between the fluid element and the planet in spherical coordinates. The smoothing parameter s is employed to avoid errors near the planet, because at the planet location the potential diverges. This smoothing parameter is calculated as (following FARGO3D documentation)

$$s = \text{RocheSmoothing} \times r \times \left(\frac{m_p}{3M_*}\right)^{1/3} = \text{RocheSmoothing} \times r \times r_{\text{Hill}}, \quad (4.7)$$

where RocheSmoothing is a value which parametrizes s and r_{Hill} is the planet's Hill radius, this is defined as (Valtonen & Karttunen, 2006)

$$r_{\text{Hill}} = a_p \sqrt[3]{\frac{m_p}{3M_*}}. \quad (4.8)$$

For the values given in table 4.1 the Hill radius is $r_{\text{Hill}} \approx 0.07$. In order to avoid numerical effects and at the same time to study fluxes near the protoplanet, a value of $\text{RocheSmoothing} = 1.5\Delta r/r_{\text{Hill}}$ (i.e. $s = 1.5\Delta r$) was chosen, where Δr is the cell size in the r coordinate.

Planet accretion

A function which extracts material of the cells near the planet was developed with the aim to perform planet accretion. The accretion is computed as

$$\rho_{\text{new}} = f\rho_{\text{old}} \quad (4.9)$$

inside a fraction λ of the Hill radius

$$r_{\text{acc}} = \lambda r_{\text{Hill}}. \quad (4.10)$$

The term ρ_{old} refers to the density obtained when the fluid equations are solved, while ρ_{new} corresponds to the new value of density after applying some function f . In general, f can be a function of position, temperature, etc. In this work a constant $f = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ is implemented like the accretion function, in order to decrease the density inside r_{acc} . The accretion was computed after each time step of the simulation (DT for the FARGO3D code).

Kley (1998) showed that in order to avoid material accumulation at the planet zone, it is correct to extract mass in a radius of the order of the Hill radius (he called it Roche’s lobe), this is equivalent to $\lambda \sim 1$ in equation (4.10). Nevertheless, this approach is not useful for this work, since circumplanetary disks form inside the Hill radius. Machida et al. (2008) showed that circumplanetary disks can be modeled if $\lambda \ll 0.1$ in the sink cell approximation. In these simulations $\lambda = 1.5\Delta r/r_{\text{Hill}}$ (i.e. $r_{\text{acc}} = 1.5\Delta r$) was used.

How do planet parameters affect simulations?

The figure 4.1 shows a Ψ vs $\xi/\Delta r$ graph for the different planet parameters described previously. The solid line represents the potential without a softening parameter ($s = 0$), while the dotted one corresponds to a value of $s = 1.5\Delta r$. Both lines follow the same behavior for points located far away from s (denoted with a labeled vertical line). Near s the softened potential separates from the non-softened one. Therefore regions around $\sigma = s$ are not well modeled by equation (4.5). In order to model correctly material near the planet, a small value of s must be chosen. On the other hand, if s was smaller than the size of a cell, the potential would diverge numerically (see solid line in Fig. 4.1). This means that very small values of s lead to numerical errors. In this work we need to model fluid near the protoplanet and at the same time avoid numerical errors. A value of $s = 1.5\Delta r$ was chosen like a large enough value to avoid numerical errors and also a small enough one for not modifying physics near the protoplanet. The logical procedure is to put the accretion radius at least at s , since the material closer to s is not well suited numerically. The figure 4.1 shows that r_{acc} and s are located at $1.5\Delta r$. With these values of s and r_{acc} we ensured that the material around the protoplanet is well suited physically. Additionally the possible numerical errors are avoided correctly.

Circumplanetary disk

A circumplanetary disk around the protoplanet is not implemented as initial condition. All previous physical parameters are enough to create an environment which simulates a protoplanet accreting material with angular momentum from a protoplanetary disk. Therefore a circumplanetary disk forms as a consequence of the physics that present in the system.

4.2 Boundary conditions (BC)

Simulating a complete disk is computationally expensive and not necessary for the objective of this work. Instead of this, the use of a correct set of boundary conditions allow us to simulate the region to be studied. Thus, we only simulate a part of the entire disk with the chosen boundary conditions described below.

Since FARGO3D is designed to study disk-like systems, the azimuthal boundaries are fixed as periodic (this cannot be changed in the current version of the code). Consequently, boundary conditions should be defined only in the other two coordinates (radius and colatitude for this case). A scheme of how the boundary conditions are implemented is shown in figure 4.2. To fix correctly all the boundary conditions, all fields must be defined at all the boundaries (X_{min}^2 , X_{max}^2 , X_{min}^3 and X_{max}^3). In this case the X^2 and X^3 variables stand for r and θ , respectively.

Default and new developed boundary conditions were used. Table 4.2 shows the implemented boundary conditions. A description of these is presented in the following subsections.

Figure 4.1: Planetary potential for different chosen parameters in the simulations. The figure shows the behavior for a softened ($s = 1.5\Delta r$, dashed-line) and a non-softened ($s = 0$, solid line) planet potential. Both potentials follow the same trend for $\xi/\Delta r \gg s$, this ensures that the softened potential models the planet influence on the fluid far away from it. For $\xi/\Delta r \sim s$, the softened potential does not follow the non-softened case.

4.2.1 Default Boundary conditions in FARGO3D

Symmetric

Symmetric BC copies the values of the active cell to the ghost zones. This condition allows material getting in or out the simulated region. Symmetric BCs are also called outflow in this kind of codes.

Antisymmetric

Antisymmetric BC copies the negative values of the active cell to the ghost ones. This condition mimic the reflection of material in a given boundary. Antisymmetric BCs are also called reflective in this kind of codes.

4.2.2 Boundaries at r

From equation (2.21) the dependence of ρ with coordinates is (in spherical coordinates)

$$\rho(r, \theta) \propto (r \sin \theta)^{-(\alpha+1)} \exp\left(-\frac{(\cos \theta)^2}{2H^2(\sin \theta)^2}\right). \quad (4.11)$$

Density boundaries at r_{\min} and r_{\max} are obtained from equation (4.11) at a constant θ_0 . From equation (4.11), the relation between ρ and a fixed value ρ_0 is

$$\rho = \rho_0 \left(\frac{r \sin \theta_0}{r_0 \sin \theta_0}\right)^{-(\alpha+1)} \exp\left(-\frac{(\cos \theta_0)^2}{2H^2(\sin \theta_0)^2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{(\cos \theta_0)^2}{2H^2(\sin \theta_0)^2}\right) = \rho_0 \left(\frac{r_0}{r}\right)^{\alpha+1}, \quad (4.12)$$

Figure 4.2: Scheme of the simulated region of the disk. The frontiers X_{\min}^2 , X_{\max}^2 , X_{\min}^3 y X_{\max}^3 restrict the simulation zone, where the correct set of boundary conditions are provided (see table 4.2). Azimuthal boundary conditions (perpendicular to the page) are periodic.

where the sub-zero values are established for the ones in the active mesh. The right-hand side part of eq. (4.12) takes a simple form because the simulated disk is not flared (the expression for a flared disk is a bit more complicated).

For the azimuthal velocity, an extrapolation of the equation (4.2) was used. This takes the form

$$v^\phi = v_0^\phi \frac{r^{-1/2} - \Omega_p r}{r_0^{-1/2} - \Omega_p r_0}. \quad (4.13)$$

The sub-zero values denote the ones in the active mesh. The other variables – v^r , v^θ , ϵ – were set as symmetric.

4.2.3 Boundaries at θ

The density boundaries at θ_{\min} are obtained from equation (4.11) at a constant r_0 . From equation (4.11), the relation between ρ and a fixed value ρ_0 is

$$\rho = \rho_0 \left(\frac{\sin \theta_0}{\sin \theta} \right)^{\alpha+1} \exp \left[\frac{1}{2H^2} \left(\frac{(\cos \theta_0)^2}{(\sin \theta_0)^2} - \frac{(\cos \theta)^2}{(\sin \theta)^2} \right) \right]. \quad (4.14)$$

For θ_{\max} , symmetric boundaries were chosen as symmetric since only half of the disk is simulated. The other variables were set as symmetric boundary conditions, except v^θ at θ_{\max} , where the antisymmetric condition was implemented to fix reflective boundaries.

	ρ	v^ϕ	v^r	v^θ	ϵ
$X_{\min}^2(r_{\min})$	extrapolation (eq. 4.12)	extrapolation (eq. 4.13)	symmetric	symmetric	symmetric
$X_{\max}^2(r_{\max})$	extrapolation (eq. 4.12)	extrapolation (eq. 4.13)	symmetric	symmetric	symmetric
$X_{\min}^3(\theta_{\min})$	extrapolation (eq. 4.14)	symmetric	symmetric	symmetric	symmetric
$X_{\max}^3(\theta_{\max})$	symmetric	symmetric	symmetric	antisymmetric	symmetric

Table 4.2: Boundary conditions used in simulations.

4.3 Domain and resolution

Because of numerical reasons some characteristics on simulations can be generated due to resolution issues. In order to discard these effects, simulations were run at different resolutions. In this way, these artifacts can be identified and taken away. A summary of domains and resolutions is given in table 4.3.

4.3.1 Low resolution simulation

A low resolution simulation of a global disk was run. This was made with the aim to demonstrate that the adopted model is capable to reproduce the usual signatures of circumstellar disk with planetary formation (such as gap opening and disk perturbations).

We simulated a complete disk in azimuth (from $-\pi$ to π), in r from 0.4 to 2.5 and in colatitude a grid of three times the aspect ratio was chosen (this is $\pi/2 - 3H \approx 1.42$ to $\pi/2$). These regions were simulated with 256, 128 and 64 cells in azimuth, radius and colatitude, respectively. We also ran a global disk simulation turning off the accretion to study the numerical effects of accretion on the circumstellar disk evolution. Accreting and non-accreting simulations are labeled as LRAG and LRNG models, respectively.

This simulation is not useful to study circumplanetary disks. Nevertheless, it is a fast way to study the correct implementation of the initial and boundary conditions and also the correct circumstellar disk evolution.

4.3.2 Medium resolution simulation

A circumplanetary disk analysis requires a higher resolution than the previous one. We developed a simulation with enough resolution to study a circumplanetary disk, but at the same time with the less cost in computational time as possible. We called this model “medium resolution” simulation.

We run three versions of this model to study accretion effects, and also the use of a “shear sheet” domain instead of a global one. The global accreting one (labeled as MRAG) is simulated with 1024, 256 and 64 in the range $-\pi$ to π , 0.4 to 1.6 and 1.42 to $\pi/2$, in azimuth, radius and colatitude, respectively. The shear sheet version of this model (labeled as MRAS) has the same cell sizes as the previous one but with a different domain in azimuth. This is 256 points in the range -0.7854 to 0.7854 , this speed up the simulation with minimum numerical errors to study circumplanetary disks (see §5.1.4). A shear sheet version of this model without accretion (labeled MRNS) also was run to study the accretion effects around the protoplanet.

With this resolution we are able to study fluxes around the protoplanet correctly. Unless it is in the limit to resolving precisely the circumplanetary disk.

	LRAG	LRNG	MRAG	MRAS	MRNS	HRAS
NX	256	256	1024	256	256	512
NY	128	128	256	256	256	512
NZ	64	64	64	64	64	96
X range	$-\pi : \pi$	$-\pi : \pi$	$-\pi : \pi$	$-0.7854 : 0.7854$	$-0.7854 : 0.7854$	$-0.7854 : 0.7854$
Y range	0.4:2.5	0.4:2.5	0.4:1.6	0.4:1.6	0.4:1.6	0.4:1.6
Z range	$1.42 : \pi/2$					
ΔX	2.45×10^{-2}	2.45×10^{-2}	6.14×10^{-3}	6.14×10^{-3}	6.14×10^{-3}	3.07×10^{-3}
ΔY	1.64×10^{-2}	1.64×10^{-2}	4.70×10^{-3}	4.70×10^{-3}	4.70×10^{-3}	2.35×10^{-3}
ΔZ	2.36×10^{-3}	1.57×10^{-3}				
Accretion	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES
Global	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO

Table 4.3: Simulation parameters for the different models used in this work. All models were ran using spherical coordinates. X is azimuth, Y is spherical radius and Z is colatitude.

4.3.3 High resolution simulation

A higher resolution simulation was made with the aim to extract the best data as possible. It has the same ranges that the medium resolution simulations (MRAS and MRNS), but it is divided in 512, 512, 96 cells in azimuth, radius and colatitude, respectively. With this simulation we have almost ten times more resolution in azimuth and radius than the low resolution one. Almost all the analysis presented in chapter 5 were made using this simulation (labeled HRAS). We specify when results from other models are used.

With this resolution the cell size for the r coordinate is $\sim 4\% r_{\text{Hill}}$, this is small enough for a correct study of circumplanetary disks. This resolution is similar to the one used by Gressel et al. (2013). Nevertheless, this simulation is far away from the ones which uses the “nested grid” method. This technique allows to reach higher resolution near the planet, reaching cell sizes of the order of the planet diameter (e.g. Tanigawa et al., 2012; Szulágyi et al., 2014). The actual version of FARGO3D does not allow to use this approach. Nevertheless, in this work we are focused on getting circumplanetary disk parameters, we are not interested in regions near the protoplanet. Therefore the HRAS model is enough for this objective.

This set of parameters is enough to simulate an isothermal disk. This model could be generalized with more general disks. Figure 4.3 shows the initial density and velocity field for the circumstellar disk. The density gradients are observed as different isocontours, while the velocity field is shown as arrows. The regions where there are no arrows corresponds to the co-rotation region (defined using equation (4.2)).

4.4 Computational Capabilities

Simulations were run at the Department of Astronomy, University of Guanajuato, Guanajuato, Gto., México. We used the server `rambutan` provided by Dr. Erick Nagel. This server has a CPU power given by an Intel®Xeon(R) CPU E5-2620 0 with 12×2.00 GHz cores and with one GPU card `NVIDIA Tesla C2050/C2070`.

Figure 4.3: Initial Conditions for the circumstellar disk. Isocontours correspond to density, labeled by I_{den} , where I_{den} is for $\log_{10} \rho$. The Arrows show the initial velocity field, which rotates with a Keplerian disk modified to corotate with the planet. The corotation region is observed in the zone where there are no arrows.

CHAPTER 5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter provides the results of the simulations together with a brief discussion. It starts in section 5.1 with a general analysis of the global evolution of the circumstellar disk, to compare with previous studies and to ensure the validity of these simulations. A discussion of the possible numerical effects due to accretion and boundaries is also presented in the first section. Section 5.2 is devoted to analyze the circumplanetary disk formation via the fluxes around the protoplanet, and to characterize the direction of the material which supplies the circumplanetary disk. Section 5.3 treats the CPD properties, such as its density, thickness, angular velocity, size and mass, in order to characterize the disk. Section 5.4 provides an analysis of the circumplanetary disk stability via the Toomre Q parameter, together with an analysis of the possible variations of the parameters which could modify Q . This chapter ends with a discussion of the implications for moon formation with the results obtained in the simulations in §5.5.

5.1 Global evolution of the circumstellar disk

5.1.1 Density waves

An embedded protoplanet in a circumstellar disk generates density wave perturbations in such a disk. These start from the L1 and L2 Lagrangian point region and propagate in the disk corotating with the planet (as was discussed in §2.2.4). These density waves are naturally generated by all planets embedded in a circumstellar disk. They have been obtained from 2D and 3D simulations for a wide range of planet masses (e.g. Kley, 1998; De Val-Borro et al., 2006; Bate et al., 2003; D'Angelo et al., 2003). Hence, these waves are a notable characteristic of embedded protoplanets in CSD. Therefore, they should appear in all these kinds of simulations.

Global disk evolution was tracked with the LRAg model (see §4.3). Cuts on the circumstellar disk midplane are shown in figure 5.1 for orbits 2, 10, 100 and 238. The low-density region at the position $X=1.0$ and $Y=0.0$ corresponds to the planet position, where material has been removed to mimic planetary accretion. It is observed that for orbit 2, density waves have not been propagated over all the disk extent. They start from the zone corresponding to the L1 and L2 Lagrangian

points and finish inside the simulation zone. At orbit 10, the density waves cover all the extent of the simulated disk. For the orbits 100 and 238 the morphology has not changed significantly, this indicates that the system has reached a stationary state. The existence of these waves are evidence of the correct treatment of the planet gravitational potential by the code.

5.1.2 Gap evolution

In addition to the density wave perturbations, an embedded Jupiter-like protoplanet opens a gap inside its corotation zone due to gravitational torques (Goldreich & Tremaine, 1979; Artymowicz & Lubow, 1994). This can be appreciated in figure 5.1, where a slight density decrease around the planet orbital region is observed. The gap opening in 3D simulations is not as efficient as in the 2D case, since 2D simulations do not have vertical flux which refill the gap (e.g. D’Angelo et al., 2002; Crida et al., 2006).

A best analysis of gap formation is through the radial mass profile given by

$$M(r) = \int_{\phi_{\min}}^{\phi_{\max}} \int_{\theta_{\min}}^{\theta_{\max}} \rho(\phi, r, \theta) r^2 \sin \theta d\theta d\phi. \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.2 represents a discrete version of equation (5.1) for the grid in this simulation scaled with the planet mass for orbits 0, 2, 4, 6, 10, 100, 200, 238. The solid line represents the initial mass profile of the circumstellar disk (orbit 0). It follows a power law $M(r) \propto r^{-0.5}$. This is a consequence of the initial conditions, where a surface density profile $\Sigma \propto r^{-1.5}$ was fixed. As the system evolves, perturbations far away from the planet are present in the mass profile due to density waves, but in general these follow the same power law profile like the initial one. Near the protoplanet, the mass profile changes drastically with respect to the initial condition. The system evolves rapidly in the first few orbits (1-20), reaching the final gap depth and width in approximately 20 orbits. For orbits 20 to 238, the gap has neither changed in shape or depth, therefore it can be concluded that the system has reached a quasi-statical state near orbit 20. Based on these results, median and high resolution simulations were run until they reached a quasi-statical state (orbit 25) in order to save computational time.

The system reached a quasi-statical state rapidly due to the boundary conditions. Radial frontiers are fixed with an extrapolation of a circumstellar disk with steady density and velocity, this does not simulate neither the star accretion nor the circumstellar disk evolution. Therefore the disk will not change drastically since the BCs keeps it stable at the frontiers. Nevertheless, there is a reason to use this approximation. As we are interested in circumplanetary disk formation and dynamics, we only evolve the system for a few of orbits, enough for a circumplanetary disk formation. For a Jupiter-like protoplanet at a distance of 5 AU this is of the order of some thousands of years, which is much less than the viscous timescale of a circumstellar disk, typically of the order of 10^5 years (Armitage, 2013), meaning that this approach is valid. To correctly analyze the long-term evolution of a circumplanetary disk in a protoplanetary disk, this approach is not useful and other boundary conditions have to be taken in consideration, such as accretion towards the star which would allow the formation of a transitional disk that should affect the circumplanetary-protoplanetary disk interaction.

Density waves and gap formation by a massive planet show that global disk evolution is equivalent to the one observed in previous works, meaning that initial and boundary conditions are correct. Circumplanetary disk analysis is therefore reliable with these simulation setups.

Figure 5.1: Circumstellar disk midplane at orbits 2 (upper-left), 10 (upper-right), 100 (lower-left) and 238 (lower-right). The lower density region at $X=1$ and $Y=0$ corresponds to the removed material which mimics planetary accretion. Density waves and a gap are visible in the disk as a consequence of the planet gravitational perturbations on the disk. These features have been observed for these kinds of disks in other studies (see text). A nice video of this evolution can be found in <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=u6tTfTStYps>.

Figure 5.2: Radial mass profile at different orbits. The initial mass profile (solid line) coincides with a typical circumstellar disk. This profile is modified by density waves and a gap in the planet position, represented by the other lines. After orbit 20 (short line-dot line) the system reaches a quasi-statical equilibrium which does not change significantly at the final orbit (four dots line).

5.1.3 Accreting vs non-accreting simulations

The accretion mechanism implemented is just an approximation in order to avoid material accumulation at the planet position, but this is far away from the real accretion mechanism of a protoplanet. This “sink cell” mechanism has been widely used in the literature with this purpose (e.g. Machida, 2009; Ayliffe & Bate, 2009b; Szulágyi et al., 2014). To convince the reader of the necessity to use this accretion mechanism, we ran low and medium resolution simulations turning off the accretion (LRNG and MRNS models, respectively), to show the problems which arise from the accumulation of material around the protoplanet.

Figure 5.3 shows an equivalent result from the global circumstellar disk (§5.1) evolution without accretion (LRNG model). Both cases show a similar disk evolution, where the density waves are located at the same position as the system evolves. The difference arises at the planet position where figure 5.3 shows a bright spot due to an excess in density, compared with figure 5.1. This does not affect the circumstellar disk evolution. Therefore the sink cell mechanism does not change the global evolution of the circumstellar disk.

Figure 5.4 shows a comparison of the gap evolution for the accreting and non-accreting simulations. Both simulations show the same gap width. The difference arises with the gap depth, this is deeper in the accreting simulation. This result is obvious in the non-accreting simulation, because material accumulates around the protoplanet position, this contributes with more mass in the gap. Both simulations reach a quasi-statical equilibrium after orbit 20, this means that the equilibrium is only a consequence of the boundary conditions. The accretion mechanism does not change this quasi-statical state. Therefore the “sink cell” accretion only regulates the mass quantity around the protoplanet.

These results show that the evolution of a circumstellar disk is not significantly affected by the sink cell accretion in this approach. Accretion only affects material around the protoplanet. In fact, material accumulation around the protoplanet does not allow circumplanetary disk formation.

Figure 5.3: Similar to figure 5.1, but in this case the accretion was turned off. The high density zone at the planet position ($X=1$ and $Y=0$) correspond to material accumulation.

Figure 5.4: Gap evolution at two different orbits for the accreting and non-accreting simulation.

Instead of this, a quasi-spherical mass agglomeration forms around the planet. This generates a flux cycle (Morbidei et al., 2014): the planet gravity attracts material from the circumstellar disk at the planet position, this material is not removed, then it accumulates there. As long as material is accumulated, its density profile generates a pressure gradient which decreases outwards from the planet. At any given point, there is enough material at the planet location, for the pressure to counteract the gravity force, thus stopping material from falling towards the planet. This generates a cycle of material which is first attracted by the planet gravity and then repelled by pressure. Since gravity is a radial force, this cycle generates a spherical envelope around the planet instead of a circumplanetary disk. We observed this for the MRNS simulation. This cycle is shown in figure 5.5 for the orbit 25. The density map shows the spherical envelope described previously, where the color gradient indicates that the highest density is located at the planet position and decrements radially further away from the protoplanet. Arrows represent the velocity field around the protoplanet. Far away from the protoplanet, vectors point towards the planet position. When they reach the high density region, they are repelled by the pressure exerted. The morphology around the protoplanet in figure 5.5 does not correspond to a disk-like structure.

Leaving aside the fact that the accretion mechanism in this work is not a correct approximation for the real mechanism around a protoplanet, it allows for studying a circumplanetary disk system since, as was shown, a non-accretion simulation is not useful for these purposes.

5.1.4 Global vs Shear sheet simulation

Reaching high resolution in a global simulation is computationally expensive. This is not reliable since we are interested in circumplanetary disks, which occupy just a little region of the circumstellar disk. A practical solution is only to simulate the region around the protoplanet, in the so called “shear sheet” approximation. Within this approach, the global circumstellar disk is not modeled, instead of this just a sheared disk (or shear sheet) is simulated, its influence on the circumplanetary disk are mimicked with the correct set of boundary conditions (e.g. Machida, 2009; Ayliffe & Bate, 2009b; Shabram & Boley, 2013).

Figure 5.5: Vertical cut at the $X=1$ plane for the non-accreting medium resolution simulation (MRNS model). A spherical mass agglomeration forms around the protoplanet. The density gradient generates a pressure which counteracts the planetary gravity force. This generates a spherical envelope which does not allow the formation of a circumplanetary disk.

The actual `FARGO3D` version does not allow to work with the boundaries in the azimuthal coordinate. Instead of this, we use the approach made by [Gressel et al. \(2013\)](#). The basic idea is to simulate only a region of the circumstellar disk around the protoplanet. This means a range in azimuth smaller than the global disk. This allows to reach high resolution with less computational cost. Nevertheless, this disk truncation generates some differences in the evolution of the system.

We ran the medium resolution simulation for the case of a global and a truncated disk (MRAG and MRAS models, respectively). Both simulations had the same resolution – i.e. the same cell sizes – but the number of cells was larger for the global disk case (see table 4.3), this slows down the simulation running. Figure 5.6 shows a map density for both simulations, they are shown in an azimuth-against-radius plot, between ranges $[-0.7:0.7]$ and $[0.4:1.6]$ in azimuth and radius, respectively. Both images have the same general form: a structure around the protoplanet, a gap in the circumstellar disk and density waves.

The first difference between both cases is the number of density waves, this is larger in the shear sheet simulation. This has a straightforward explanation. The `FARGO3D` code uses periodic boundary conditions in the azimuthal frontiers. This makes sense when a global disk is simulated, since the material at π is copied to $-\pi$, which corresponds to a continuous circle. On the other hand, the shear sheet simulation copies material from an angle ϕ_{\min} to ϕ_{\max} , therefore the material reaches that position $2\pi/(\phi_{\max} - \phi_{\min})$ times faster. This brings as a consequence an artificially larger number of density waves which perturbs the circumstellar disk material. A clear example is the density wave which ends at -0.7 and immediately is copied at 0.7 in right panel of the figure 5.6. This effect is purely numerical, it does not have a physical sense. While the density wave in the global disk which ends at -0.7 has to complete an angle of $2\pi - 1.4$ to reach the position 0.7 (this is not observed in the figure, it occurs at a larger radius).

Figure 5.6: Maps of density in an azimuth vs radius plot. The global disk simulation (left) shows a more stable solution in comparison with the shear disk simulation (right). The shear disk shows more density waves perturbations because they have to travel just a fraction of the grid to repeat themselves. Nevertheless, material around the protoplanet is practically unaffected.

It is visible in figure 5.6 that the region around the protoplanet is practically unaffected. Density waves only affect the circumstellar disk material, their effects on the gap region are negligible. An important fact is that both simulations reach a quasi-static equilibrium at the orbit 20 inside the gap zone (i.e. the gap has reached its maximum depth and width). Nevertheless, the shear disk does not reach the equilibrium outside the gap, the circumstellar disk profile continues changing due the great number of density waves.

These results have shown that the shear sheet approximation is not useful to study circumstellar disk evolution for the numerical artifacts which arise. On the other hand, the circumplanetary disk region is practically unaffected, there are little numerical errors, but this approach is worth it due to the speed up in computational time.

5.2 Circumplanetary disk formation

We ran the high resolution simulation (HRAS model) until the orbit 25, at this time a disk-like structure around the protoplanet position has been formed. Figure 5.7 (upper) shows the density around the protoplanet in the midplane. The central region corresponds to the accretion zone, where material has been removed. Around this region there is a disk-like structure. The circumplanetary disk structure is connected to the circumstellar disk via two spiral arms, these can be seen in the figure. Figure 5.7 (lower) shows the vertical density distribution around the protoplanet at the plane $X=1.0$. The disk-like structure can be observed in the high density region, where a torus structure is formed around the protoplanet, this can be observed via the isocontours. The surroundings outside

the torus region correspond to circumstellar material interacting with the circumplanetary disk. All these features have been observed in previous studies (e.g. Machida, 2009; Szulágyi et al., 2014). Therefore figure 5.7 shows a density distribution which corresponds to a circumplanetary disk. A nicer example of the 3D circumplanetary disk structure is shown in figure 5.8. Qualitatively, we can appreciate that this disk is not axisymmetric and is thick, compared to a protoplanetary one. These characteristics are a consequence of the material fluxes between the circumplanetary and circumstellar disks.

5.2.1 2D fluxes around the protoplanet

Fluxes around a protoplanet embedded in a circumplanetary disk are complex. In order to analyze the direction of the material from the protoplanetary disk towards the circumplanetary disk and *vice versa*, the fluxes in the midplane and in the vertical direction were obtained. The upper image of figure 5.9 shows the velocity vectors over a density map in the midplane. Around the planet position ($X=1.0$ and $Y=0.0$), velocity vectors trace an orbital motion, this corresponds to the circumplanetary disk region. This rotation is inside the Hill radius (limited by the shadowed region in the figure). Outside the Hill region, fluxes on the spiral arms are moving material far away from the planet region. This means that these spiral arms move material from the circumplanetary disk to the protoplanetary disk. Therefore we found outflow fluxes at the midplane in our simulation.

There is a discussion in the literature about the direction of the midplane fluxes, some simulations found inflow (e.g. Ayliffe & Bate, 2009b) and other ones outflow (e.g. Klahr & Kley, 2006; Ayliffe & Bate, 2012; Tanigawa et al., 2012). Szulágyi et al. (2014) showed that the direction of the fluxes depends on the viscosity. Their viscous simulation shows outflow fluxes while their inviscid simulation inflow ones. This is explained since in the inviscid simulation shocks are stronger than in a viscous one, these shocks slow the flux, therefore material can be accreted inward the protoplanet. On the other hand, the shocks in the viscous simulation are not strong enough to stop the material and then it can escape via the spiral arms.

In this work an inviscid simulation is assumed, by following Szulágyi et al. (2014) we should have found inflow fluxes, why did we find outflow fluxes? The explanation comes from numerical issues. We have not implemented an implicit viscosity in the equations (i.e. we set the Shakura & Sunyaev parameter α_ν equal to zero). But, there is a “numerical viscosity” which arises from the numerical errors at the last bytes of a variable when operations are performed by the computer (a good discussion can be found in Toro, 2009). This kind of errors are practically negligible in the majority of cases. Planetary formation is not one of these. It has been found that protoplanets are created in very low viscosity regions called “dead zones” (see Thommes et al., 2008), this means that small artificial viscosity effects could be bigger than the real viscosity in these regions. This will change significantly the viscosity around a protoplanet. Szulágyi et al. (2014) found that these effects are minimized with higher resolution simulations. These numerical errors are responsible for the viscosity in our simulation, this is why we obtained outflow fluxes at the midplane. It is possible that other works with prescribed zero viscosity showed outflow fluxes also due to this numerical viscosity (e.g. Tanigawa et al., 2012). Therefore the material which supplies the circumplanetary disk in this work is not made via midplane fluxes. There must be another way to feed the CPD.

A vertical cut at the plane $X=1.0$ with velocity vectors on a density map is shown in the lower image of figure 5.7. We can see that vectors point towards to the circumplanetary disk (rather inside or outside the Hill sphere). This implies that the circumplanetary disk is supplied from material which comes from outside the midplane from a vertical inflow. The principal mechanism to transport material from the protoplanetary to the circumplanetary disk is via vertical inflow. This result is in agreement with other works (e.g. Tanigawa et al., 2012; Ayliffe & Bate, 2009a).

Figure 5.7: Density distribution around the protoplanet in the midplane (upper figure) and vertical cut at the $X=1$ plane. Solid lines represent 20 isocontours equispaced from $\log_{10}(\rho) = -5.783$ to -0.5407 (I_{den} in the figure). The highest density regions correspond to the circumplanetary disk.

Figure 5.8: 3D view of the circumplanetary disk around the planet position. Solid surfaces represent density isocontours of $\log_{10} \rho$ (l_{den} in the figure). A disk-like structure is clearly visible. The circle represents a map density at the midplane of the circumstellar disk of radius $1r_{Hill}$.

In our model the circumplanetary disk is formed from circumstellar disk material which comes from the vertical direction. At the midplane the circumplanetary disk transport material to the protoplanetary disk via the spiral arms.

We have discussed that [Szulágyi et al. \(2014\)](#) found inflow fluxes at the midplane, does this change the conclusion about the vertical feed of the circumplanetary disk? They quantified the total material which is supplied to the circumplanetary disk for their simulation. They found that midplane fluxes count only for the 10% of the total flux which feed the CPD. The other 90% is due to vertical – they called polar – inflow. Therefore the direction of the midplane fluxes does not matter, circumplanetary disks forms mainly with circumstellar disk material which comes from the vertical direction.

5.2.2 3D fluxes around the protoplanet

A better way to understand the flux distribution around the protoplanet is to analyze the radial flux (ρv_{ξ}) directions to an observer at the planet position. From the analysis presented by [Tanigawa et al. \(2012\)](#), the radial velocity v_{ξ} – measured at the planet position – is calculated as

$$v_{\xi} = \frac{\vec{v} \cdot \vec{\xi}}{|\vec{\xi}|}, \quad (5.2)$$

where \vec{v} is the corotating velocity in rectangular coordinates and $\vec{\xi}$ is the distance vector between the planet position (x_p, y_p, z_p) and a fluid element (with position x, y, z). This distance vector is calculated as

$$\vec{\xi} = (x - x_p)\hat{i} + (y - y_p)\hat{j} + (z - z_p)\hat{k}. \quad (5.3)$$

Figure 5.9: Velocity vectors distribution on the circumplanetary disk midplane (Upper) and at the plane $X=1$ (lower). The Hill radius is limited by the shadowed circle in the upper figure.

Therefore ρv_ξ is the radial flux which would measure an observer placed at the planet location. If we measure the flux ρv_ξ at a radius ξ_0 , we may obtain the flux distribution on that sphere. Figure 5.10 shows the flux ρv_ξ for two spheres of radii $0.5 r_{\text{Hill}}$ and $1.0 r_{\text{Hill}}$ (0.035 and 0.07 for these simulations, respectively). Each sphere is divided into two regions, the inward and outward flux regions. The zero flux region – it marks the transition between the two zones – is denoted with a solid line. The outward flux region is found near the sphere equator, which corresponds to the circumplanetary disk midplane. This zone coincides with the arms which connect the circumplanetary and the protoplanetary disk in figures 5.7 and 5.9. From these figures we can see that spiral arms are thick and vary with the radius. The spiral arm of this figure is the spiral observed at the left side of figure 5.9 (upper image). The inward flux region covers a larger area than the outward fluxes one, for both spheres. It is important to notice that at the sphere poles there are only inward fluxes, this shows in a 3D view that the accretion towards the CPD is made by polar inflows. These results are consistent with Tanigawa et al. (2012) (see their figure 5 and discussion).

5.2.3 How does material join to the disk?

Previous results allow to obtain the flux distribution around the protoplanet and get how the circumplanetary disk is supplied via polar inflow of material. A 3D picture of the fluxes around the planet is shown in figure 5.11. Solid lines represent streamlines – which describe the motion of a fluid element – over a density map. It is observed that the material comes from high altitudes, then falls towards the circumplanetary disk. This falling material joins the circumplanetary disk and rotates around the protoplanet.

Let us analyze qualitatively how the material couples to the circumplanetary disk. Material far away from the planet feels the gravitational potential and then is accelerated. This acceleration generates that the material just above the protoplanet has an almost free-fall velocity (since it is passing a low density region). At this moment, the fluid element has a kinetic energy given by their current free fall velocity and its (low) density. Near the CPD, this fluid element could follow two paths: to reach the high density region which corresponds to the circumplanetary disk or to continue in a low density medium (outside the circumplanetary disk).

For the first case, the fluid element has a given kinetic energy, just before passing the high density region. Once it reaches this zone, it has the same energy, but now the density is larger. This means that –by following the energy conservation principle– if the density grows the velocity has to decrease, this stops the previous free-fall motion. This abrupt velocity change generates a shock which dissipates energy. In this way the material can join the CPD. A better analysis of these shocks is via Bernoulli integrals which demonstrate the formation of shocks at the circumplanetary disk surface. This analysis is out of the scope of this thesis, the interested reader can find it in Tanigawa et al. (2012). Figure 5.12 shows a close up around the protoplanet and the circumplanetary disk formation. The streamlines are almost vertical just above the CPD. It can be observed that streamlines bend near the disk surface, due to the previous described mechanism. After they turn because of the density change and are coupled to the orbital motion of the disk around the protoplanet.

On the other hand, there is material which has a free-fall velocity near the protoplanet but does not reach the circumplanetary disk surface. Then it is not stopped (since it continues the fall into a low density medium). This material reaches the circumstellar disk midplane with a high velocity, therefore it is not captured by the planet potential. This allows material to escape from the Hill zone via the spiral arms. Figure 5.11 shows this behavior. Some stream lines are accelerated by the planet potential towards the circumplanetary disks, if they do not reach the high density region, they follow a path via the spiral arms. This mechanism resupplies the protoplanetary disk.

Figure 5.10: Flux ρv_ξ at the surface of two spheres of radii $1.0 r_{\text{Hill}}$ (upper) and $0.5 r_{\text{Hill}}$ (lower) (0.07 and 0.035 for these simulations, respectively). Solid line represents the region where $\rho v_\xi = 0$, then there are two regions divided by this line, an outward (red) and an inward (blue) fluxes regions. This figure is equivalent to the Figure 5 of [Tanigawa et al. \(2012\)](#).

Figure 5.11: 3D distribution of fluxes around a protoplanet. Solid lines correspond to streamlines of fluid elements. Some of these lines join to the disk rotation, becoming part of the circumplanetary disk. Other ones escape via the spiral arms. Solid surfaces are cuts in the protoplanetary disk.

Figure 5.12: Close up to the circumplanetary disk with stream lines. Solid iso-surfaces show the density distribution which coincides with a disk-like structure. Solid lines represent the fluid stream lines, some of them are coupled to the CPD rotation due to the abrupt density change.

Let us summarize this section. Once the system has reached a quasi-static state we determined the structure of the flux distribution around the protoplanet. The morphology of this coincides with a disk-like which we identified like the circumplanetary disk. Around the protoplanet there are both inflowing and outflowing fluxes. The outflow region coincides with the spiral arms which connect the CSD with the CPD. The inflow region is dominant over the outflow one. Mainly through the perpendicular to the circumplanetary disk axis. Therefore the inflow of material to the circumplanetary disk is a polar inflow. The material which joins into the circumplanetary disk is because of shocks at the disk surface, these shocks are generated by the abrupt density change between the circumplanetary disk and the material outside it.

5.3 Circumplanetary disk properties

5.3.1 Density distribution

The mass distribution in the disk is quantified via the density at the midplane and the surface density. Figures 5.7 and 5.8 show a qualitative picture of the mass distribution of the circumplanetary disk. In order to obtain a quantitative analysis, we calculated the azimuthally averaged profiles of the midplane density, ρ_{CPD} , and the surface density, Σ_{CPD} (see eq. (2.17) for a relation between surface and volumetric densities).

Figure 5.13 shows the data points obtained for the HRAS simulation for the azimuthally averaged density at midplane and the surface density (respectively in panels (a) and (b)). One can observe how the profiles follow a power law inside the Hill radius. They start to deviate from the power law near the Hill radius and beyond. This indicates a well established mass distribution around the protoplanet within the Hill region. Both curves were fitted with a power law in the range of Hill radius given by $[0.1 - 0.8]$. The relation for the azimuthally averaged midplane density is

$$\rho_{\text{CPD}} = 6.7(\pm 0.16) \times 10^{-7} r^{-3.02 \pm 0.02}, \quad (5.4)$$

and the azimuthally averaged surface density is

$$\Sigma_{\text{CPD}} = 7.5(\pm 0.8) \times 10^{-7} r^{-1.87 \pm 0.03}, \quad (5.5)$$

both in code units. The reported errors come from the small dispersion of the simulated data. The power law exponent found for midplane and surface densities coincide with previous works. [Aylyffe & Bate \(2009a\)](#) reported $\rho_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-2} - r^{-3/2}$. [Tanigawa et al. \(2012\)](#) released the values $\rho_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-3}$ and $\Sigma_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-3/2}$. The relations (5.4) and (5.5) show that – in general – the mass distribution in a circumplanetary disk drops faster than for a circumstellar disk. Therefore the majority of mass in circumstellar disks is near the protoplanet. This behavior will help to characterize the size of the circumplanetary disk (see §5.3.4).

It is possible to analyze if the circumplanetary disk has reached hydrostatic equilibrium. In equilibrium, the surface density should be related with the midplane density as (see §2.1.3)

$$\Sigma \propto h\rho. \quad (5.6)$$

If we assume $h \propto r$ – i.e. a not flared disk – this relation is almost satisfied for the obtained $\Sigma_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-1.9}$ and $\rho_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-3}$ profiles. Therefore the circumplanetary disk has reached a quasi-hydrostatic equilibrium between the gravitational force and the pressure (e.g. [Aylyffe & Bate, 2009a](#); [Tanigawa et al., 2012](#)). This equilibrium is not reached totally because of the continuous vertical fluxes which supply material into the circumplanetary disk.

Figure 5.13: Circumplanetary disk azimuthally averaged density at the midplane (a) and surface density (b). Filled circles are the azimuthally averaged values obtained from the simulation. Solid line represents a power law fitted to the data points from 0.1 to $0.8r_{\text{Hill}}$.

5.3.2 Thickness

Since a quasi-hydrostatic equilibrium is reached by the CPD, we can estimate its scale height. Figure 5.8 shows that the circumplanetary disk is thick. In order to calculate the disk thickness in a quantitative way, the circumplanetary disk scale height h_{CPD} is calculated. From equation (2.19), we have

$$h_{\text{CPD}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{\Sigma_{\text{CPD}}}{\rho_{\text{CPD}}}. \quad (5.7)$$

From relations (5.4) and (5.5) in (5.7) it follows that

$$h_{\text{CPD}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{7.5 \times 10^{-7} r^{-1.9}}{6.7 \times 10^{-7} r^{-3}} \approx 0.4 r^{1.1}. \quad (5.8)$$

From this result we can infer that the circumplanetary disk is thick in comparison with a circumstellar disk (the simulated circumstellar disk in this work has $h = 0.05r$). This result agrees with previous works which have also found thick circumplanetary disks (e.g. [Ayliffe & Bate, 2009a](#); [Tanigawa et al., 2012](#); [Shabram & Boley, 2013](#), they all found disks with $h_{\text{CPD}} > 0.2$). It has also been obtained that circumplanetary disks do not have an axisymmetric thickness, this varies with azimuth as a wavy structure. This is a direct consequence of pressure exerted by the polar inflow on the circumplanetary disk ([Szulágyi et al., 2014](#)). A qualitative view of this non-axisymmetric feature can be observed in figure 5.8, therefore the $h_{\text{CPD}} \approx 0.4 r^{1.1}$ profile is only an averaged value.

We cannot conclude if the disk is or is not flared, our result is in the limit of a flared disk. Both kind of disks have been reported in the literature. [Machida \(2009\)](#) and [Tanigawa et al. \(2012\)](#) have found flared disk, while [Ayliffe & Bate \(2009a\)](#) found non flared disks. It seems that if a circumplanetary disk is or is not flared depends on the simulation parameters and on the thermal treatment of the gas. On the other hand, [Szulágyi et al. \(2014\)](#) showed that circumplanetary disks are not axisymmetric. This means that a disk could be flared or not depending on the planetocentric azimuth. Therefore we cannot conclude if circumplanetary disks are flared or not. With our result we can only conclude that circumplanetary disks are thick in comparison with protoplanets.

5.3.3 Angular velocity

Figure 5.12 shows that material falls into the circumplanetary disk and then is incorporated to the disk in a circular motion. The next step is to characterize the rotation profile of the circumplanetary disk. We made this via the angular velocity, defined as

$$\vec{\Omega} = \frac{\vec{\xi} \times \vec{v}}{|\vec{\xi}|^2}, \quad (5.9)$$

where $\vec{\xi}$ is the distance vector between the fluid and the planet given in equation (5.3), and \vec{v} is the corotating velocity. Since we are only interested on the circumplanetary disk rotation around the planet, we focus on the vertical component of the angular momentum, given by

$$\Omega_z = \vec{\Omega} \cdot \hat{k}, \quad (5.10)$$

where \hat{k} is the unit vector normal to the X-Y plane. The result from the simulated data is plotted in figure 5.14(a) with filled (red) dots. We fitted a power law to these points, this gave the relation

$$\Omega_z = 1.1(\pm 0.1) \times 10^{-2} r^{-1.71 \pm 0.02}, \quad (5.11)$$

Figure 5.14: Angular velocity Ω_z at the midplane of the CPD. (Upper) Simulated data is denoted as filled circles, the solid line represents the fitted power law; dashed-line denotes the theoretical keplerian profile generated by a planet with mass $m_p = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ in this system of units. (Lower) The ratio $\Omega_z/\Omega_{\text{Kepler}}$ is shown, it is observed that the CPD has a sub-keplerian rotation.

in code units. The reported errors come from the small dispersion of the simulated data. The relation $\Omega_z \propto r^{-1.7}$ shows that the angular velocity is near Keplerian ($\Omega_{\text{kepler}} \propto r^{-1.5}$). Nevertheless, the rotation is not keplerian. Figure 5.14(a) shows the fitted power law (solid line) *vs* the theoretical Keplerian profile (dotted line), this was calculated by the planet mass used in the simulation ($m_p = 1 \times 10^{-3}$). The circumplanetary disk rotation curve is below the Keplerian one, this means that the rotation is subkeplerian at the midplane. This sub-keplerian rotation has been reported previously (e.g. Tanigawa et al., 2012; Szulágyi et al., 2014).

Figure 5.14(b) shows the ratio $\Omega_z/\Omega_{\text{kepler}}$ for different radii. Near the planet, the disk rotates with 90% the keplerian velocity, this value decreases when r increases, finishing at the Hill radius, where circumplanetary disk has a rotation $< 20\%\Omega_{\text{kepler}}$.

Figure 5.15 shows the ratio $\Omega_z/\Omega_{\text{kepler}}$ on the plane $X = 1$ around the protoplanet inside the Hill radius. It is observed that outside the midplane, there is also sub-Keplerian rotation (red zones). This means that all the disk rotates with this behavior, not just the midplane region. Szulágyi et al. (2014) found super-keplerian motion near the disk layer in their inviscid simulation, this is explained by pressure gradients near its surface. Nevertheless, their viscous simulation did not show this super-keplerian behavior, since viscosity limits the vertical pressure. Therefore in general we expect that circumplanetary disks rotate with a sub-keplerian profile. Keplerian or super-Keplerian rotation depends on the viscosity and appears just at the disk surface.

Figure 5.15 shows some extreme values of the ratio $\Omega_z/\Omega_{\text{kepler}}$: negative ratio (blue zones) and super-Keplerian ratio (yellow zones). This ratio can be negative because Ω_z is calculated using equations (5.9) and (5.10), this value is not constrained to be positive. On the other hand, Ω_{kepler} should always be positive by its definition. First thing to note, they are far from the disk structure (this is given by the isocontours), those zones are not part of the disk. Second, if we compare with other output files at different times, we observe that those features are not maintained in time. they appear stochastically as a consequence of the gas interaction there. Therefore these extreme values are not important for the conclusions of this work.

There is another interesting behavior that we can observe from figure 5.14: outside the Hill radius the angular velocity changes its sign, this indicates that the material rotates in the opposite direction. This effect is explained because inside the Hill region, material follows orbits affected by the planet potential, this creates prograde orbits with respect to the planet. Gas far away from the Hill radius, rotates with keplerian velocity around the star. In the frame rotating with the planet, this velocity moves in opposite direction to the circumplanetary disk. Therefore the angular velocity calculated via eq. (4.2) is negative. This is also discussed – with more detail – in Machida (2009).

Gravity vs pressure

This sub-Keplerian behavior is explained by a competition between the gravitational force and the pressure gradients. Let us analyze this with a simple toy model. Gas at a distance r from the planet feels two forces: the gravitational and the pressure. This is given by

$$-\nabla\psi_p - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dr}. \quad (5.12)$$

The planet potential ψ_p is given by $-Gm_p/r^2$. If we assume an isothermal equation of state, the pressure is given by $p = c_s\rho$. We can assume that c_s is constant in the circumplanetary disk and we have found that density varies with a power law as $\rho = \rho_0 r^{-\beta}$, with $\beta > 0$ (we found that $\beta = 3$). Therefore the pressure force is

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp}{dr} = -\frac{\beta c_s^2 \rho_0 r^{-(\beta+1)}}{\rho_0 r^{-\beta}} = -\beta c_s^2 r^{-1}. \quad (5.13)$$

Figure 5.15: Ratio $\Omega_z/\Omega_{\text{kepler}}$ around the protoplanet inside the Hill radius at the plane $X=1$. The circumplanetary disk region has a subkeplerian rotation around the planet. Solid lines represent 10 isocontours equispaced from $\log_{10} \rho = -2.1$ to -0.047 , to roughly plot the circumplanetary disk extension.

The competition between both forces is

$$-\frac{Gm_p}{r^2} + \frac{\beta c_s^2}{r}. \quad (5.14)$$

From equation (5.14), the material near the protoplanet feels the gravitational force plus a correction by pressure gradients. Close to the protoplanet the gravitational force dominates over the pressure, this explains the quasi-Keplerian rotation near the protoplanet. The gravity (r^{-2}) force drops faster than the pressure force (r^{-1}). Therefore the pressure dominates over the gravity at larger radii. This explains the departure from the Keplerian rotation when r is larger.

The same conclusion can be obtained for an adiabatic gas, in this case the pressure force is γ times stronger than for the isothermal case (where γ is the adiabatic index). The isothermal gas has a lower pressure ($p \propto \rho$) than an adiabatic one ($p \propto \rho^\gamma$). Therefore an adiabatic gas should have more pressure force. This should change the angular velocity profile. Machida (2009) studied the thermal effects on circumplanetary disks using different EOS. He found that near the protoplanet the rotation profile does not change significantly using different EOS, since the gravitational dominance of the planet is always reached for planets with masses $> 100M_\oplus$. At the same time, Machida found morphological disk differences for different EOS, since far away from the protoplanet the thermal effects are dominant. An isothermal disk is thicker than an adiabatic one: the stronger pressure – in adiabatic models – balances gravity closer to the midplane, this yields a thinner disk. He concludes that different EOS change the disk morphology far away from the protoplanet. However, they do not change the angular momentum on the circumplanetary disk for massive planets. Therefore our isothermal approach is valid in order to estimate the angular velocity behavior in the circumplanetary disk.

5.3.4 Size

From figure 5.9 it can be observed that the circumplanetary disk is smaller than the planet's Hill radius, then its size should be just a fraction of the Hill radius. If we assume an equilibrium between the centrifugal force and the gravitational potential, a typical CPD radius should be $\sim r_{\text{Hill}}/3$ (Quillen & Trilling, 1998).

In the following lines we show the calculation presented in Ayliffe & Bate (2009b) – they based their result on Quillen & Trilling (1998) – to obtain this value. The Lagrangian points are in resonance with the planet rotation, this means that their angular velocity is also Ω_p . Their positions with respect to the star are

$$r_L = r_p \pm r_{\text{Hill}}, \quad (5.15)$$

for L1 (-) and L2 (+). The gas captured in some Lagrange point would have a specific angular momentum relative to the protoplanet given by

$$j \simeq r_{\text{Hill}}^2 \Omega_p, \quad (5.16)$$

where r_{Hill} is the distance between the gas and the planet and Ω_p its angular velocity at that position. If we assume angular momentum conservation, at some point r_c the centrifugal potential (calculated as j^2/r_c^2 , j is taken from eq. (5.16)) is equal to the planetary gravitational potential. This point is called *centrifugal radius*, and at this point the material should be able to rotate around the planet. Therefore

$$\frac{j^2}{r_c^2} \approx \frac{Gm_p}{r_c}. \quad (5.17)$$

If we solve for r_c , we have

$$r_c = \frac{j^2}{Gm_p} = \frac{r_{\text{Hill}}^4 \Omega_p^2}{Gm_p} = \frac{r_{\text{Hill}}^4 GM_*/r_p^3}{Gm_p}, \quad (5.18)$$

if we remember the definition of Hill radius, $r_{\text{Hill}} = r_p(m_p/3M_*)^{1/3}$ (Valtonen & Karttunen, 2006), then

$$r_c = \frac{r_{\text{Hill}}^4}{3r_{\text{Hill}}^3} = \frac{1}{3}r_{\text{Hill}}. \quad (5.19)$$

This means that the orbits are truncated at $r_c \approx 1/3r_{\text{Hill}}$. This should be a typical size for a circumplanetary disk (Quillen & Trilling, 1998; Ayliffe & Bate, 2009a).

Figures 5.13 and 5.14 show that density, surface density and angular momentum are continuous from the planet position until the Hill radius, then these results cannot be used to estimate the disk size. Some alternative methods have been used in order to estimate disk sizes quantitatively. Ayliffe & Bate (2009a) found that the specific angular momentum peaks near $r_{\text{Hill}}/3$, they defined this criterion as the disk radius. Martin & Lubow (2011) found that stable orbits in a CPD are truncated by tidal forces at a radius $\sim 0.4r_{\text{Hill}}$. Tanigawa et al. (2012) defined the circumplanetary disk radius as the region where the radial velocity at the circumplanetary disk midplane is negligible, they obtained a value of $\sim 0.2r_{\text{Hill}}$.

In this work we use the method described in Shabram & Boley (2013). They defined the CPD limit as the region where the disk is truncated in mass. They plot the cumulative mass as function of the radius. There is a transition between a fast growing cumulative mass near the planet until $\sim r_{\text{Hill}}/3$. Beyond this point the cumulative mass is almost constant, meaning that there is no

Figure 5.16: Cumulative mass and density at the midplane of the CPD. Solid line with points shows the behavior obtained with the simulation. Vertical dashed line indicates the radius $r_{\text{Hill}}/3$, which defines the circumplanetary disk size.

more a significant contribution to the disk mass. Therefore, with this method, the CPD mass is contained inside $\sim r_{\text{Hill}}/3$, defining in this way the CPD radius. Figure 5.16 shows the cumulative mass and density –both at the midplane– for the simulated data. It is observed a similar behavior as in Shabram & Boley (2013). From the planet position until near a third of the Hill radius, the cumulative mass (density) is growing in a fast way. The cumulative mass (density) is almost constant far away from this point. Therefore we will also take the circumplanetary disk radius as $r_{\text{Hill}}/3$. In this way we agree with the mentioned previous works.

Different methods have given similar results for the circumplanetary disk radius, in the range of $[0.2-0.4] r_{\text{Hill}}$. These results are in agreement with first observational results about circumplanetary disk sizes (e.g. Isella et al., 2014, they found a circumplanetary disk radius of $0.4r_{\text{Hill}}$).

5.3.5 Mass

To define if circumplanetary disks are ideal places for moon formation, it is very important to estimate the total mass available in the CPD.

Figure 5.16 shows only the mass at the midplane. This is not useful to estimate the total mass inside the circumplanetary disk. In order to calculate the total mass we did as follows: the surface density contains the total mass of the disk per surface area. It can be assumed that the disk is a circle with radius $r_{\text{Hill}}/3$ (see §5.3.4). Therefore the total mass can be estimated by calculating the cumulative surface density contained inside this circumplanetary disk area.

Figure 5.17 shows the cumulative total CPD mass. At one third of the Hill radius, there is a total circumplanetary disk mass of (within $1/3r_{\text{Hill}}$)

$$m_{\text{CPD}} \approx 0.03m_{\text{p}}. \quad (5.20)$$

Therefore the circumplanetary disk has a mass of the order of 3% of the mass of the planet. We have to keep in mind that our simulation gives the mass around the protoplanet starting from a minimum radius $\sim 4\%r_{\text{Hill}}$ due to the accretion mechanism used (for the HRAS simulation). We are missing the mass inside this region, hence we are sub-estimating the total CPD mass. However, our result is a good estimate for two reasons: First, the missing mass just would move the graphic in figure 5.17 vertically, since we are plotting cumulative mass, and our method to calculate mass is not hardly affected. Second, the area that we are missing is very small, then the missed mass should not change the order of magnitude of the estimated mass. Therefore our result is a good estimate of the mass of the circumplanetary disk.

A circumplanetary disk of 3% the planet mass is in agreement with previous works (e.g. Machida, 2009; Tanigawa et al., 2012). At the same time, some observations suggest that CPD have masses lower than 10% the host planet mass (e.g. Isella et al., 2014). Other interesting result is that this mass corresponds to the gas mass. If we assume a canonical dust to gas ratio of 0.01, the circumplanetary disk has a dust mass of 0.03% or 3×10^{-4} , this corresponds to the planet to satellites system ratio found by Canup & Ward (2006). This result will be discussed with more detail in section 5.5.

5.4 Disk stability

At this point we have obtained all the necessary parameters in order to calculate the Q parameter. In this way we can quantify the disk stability. This is done with the parameter Q , defined as (Toomre, 1964)

Figure 5.17: Cumulative mass around the protoplanet. The dashed line marks the point $1/3r_{\text{Hill}}$, which corresponds to a mass of $\sim 3\%$ the planet mass.

$$Q = \frac{\kappa c_s}{\pi G \Sigma}. \quad (5.21)$$

In the simplest way, if $Q > 1$ the disk is stable, otherwise the disk is unstable and tends to collapse.

In our unitless system we can estimate Q directly from the previous found values. Since we have assumed a vertically isothermal disk, the sound velocity did not change its initial value. The circumplanetary disk size is small enough to assume that the CPD has the same sound speed as the one at the planet position. In this way we assume that the sound speed is constant in the CPD. From eq. (4.4), the sound velocity is $c_s = 0.05$. The surface density Σ_{CPD} has been obtained in section 5.3.1. In our unitless system $G = 1$. From equation (2.31), we can calculate the epicyclic frequency κ . We found that $\Omega = \Omega_0 r^{-1.7}$, then

$$r \frac{d\Omega^2}{dr} = r \Omega_0^2 (-3.4) r^{-4.4} = -3.4 \Omega^2. \quad (5.22)$$

Therefore the epicyclic frequency is (see eq. (2.31))

$$\kappa = \pm \sqrt{4\Omega^2 + r \frac{d\Omega^2}{dr}} = \pm \sqrt{4\Omega^2 - 3.4\Omega^2} \approx \pm 0.775\Omega. \quad (5.23)$$

This is only a fraction of the angular velocity of the CPD. This is a direct consequence of its sub-Keplerian profile. We take the positive value of κ in order to obtain a physical solution, then $\kappa = 0.775 |\Omega|$.

Based on these results, we are able to obtain the Q radial profile. Figure 5.18 shows the Q radial profile from 0.1 to $1r_{\text{Hill}}$ once the disk has reached a quasi-static equilibrium (orbit 25). It is observed that for all these radii $Q \gg 1$, this means that the disk is highly stable. Inside the

Figure 5.18: Radial profile of Q (solid line), κ (long-dashed line), c_s (short-dashed line) and Σ (dotted line), once the disk has reached a quasi-statical equilibrium (orbit 25). Q is much larger than unity inside the Hill radius, meaning that the circumplanetary disk is highly stable.

disk radius ($1/3r_{\text{Hill}}$) Q is larger than 100. Therefore the circumplanetary disk does not present gravitational instabilities and there are no collapses due to self-gravity.

Let us analyze the figure 5.18 with more detail. From equation (5.21), the disk stability is given by the sound velocity and the epicyclic frequency, the larger they are the more stable the disk is (since Q grows). We can see that κ is several order of magnitudes larger than c_s . This means that dynamics stabilize the disk more than thermodynamics. The sound velocity depends on the temperature, which in turn depends on the thermal properties of the gas, then this value could change depending on the model. Disk dynamics near the protoplanet only depend on the planet mass. We do not expect that this value changes drastically for a different circumplanetary disk. This result implies that – since dynamics dominate over thermodynamics – circumplanetary disks are stabilized principally by their sub-Keperian dynamics, this could be even true for more general thermal treatments. This conclusion implies that even a cold disk could be stable (a more detailed discussion is presented in §5.4.1).

The next subsections describe the role of the different parameters in equation (5.21) to analyze the possible variation of the Q value for different models.

5.4.1 Dependence on equation of state

The sound speed c_s depends directly on the thermal treatment of the gas, given by the equation of state. In our isothermal simulation, the EOS is just a relation between the pressure and the density. It does not allow a thermal evolution of the system, since we are fixing the temperature at a given radius in all the simulation. What would happen for a disk with an adiabatic or a more general EOS?

The adiabatic equation of state relates the pressure and density as

$$p = k\rho^\gamma, \quad (5.24)$$

where k is the bulk modulus and γ the adiabatic index. The sound speed is then

$$c_s = \frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma p}{\rho}}. \quad (5.25)$$

This means that the adiabatic sound speed is larger than the isothermal one by a factor $\sqrt{\gamma}$. This is related directly with the gas temperature. Therefore an adiabatic equation of state generates a hotter gas.

The energy equation of an adiabatic EOS allows thermal evolution. The internal energy ε is related with the density as

$$\varepsilon = \frac{k\rho^{\gamma-1}}{(\gamma-1)}. \quad (5.26)$$

This means that high density regions elevate the internal energy, hence the temperature ($T \propto \varepsilon$, assuming equipartition of energy). From this analysis, an isothermal disk is the coldest possible one, since it does not allow gas to get hotter. Therefore more realistic disks should be hotter, this would contribute to make the Q parameter larger, then the circumplanetary disk would be more stable.

5.4.2 Dependence on planet mass

Let us assume that the disk rotates in a Keplerian way, then κ depends directly on the planet mass. For a large mass the factor κ is large too. From this analysis, smaller planets would generate a small κ parameter, therefore a smaller Q parameter should be obtained.

Nevertheless, even if κ can be reduced theoretically to obtain a smaller Q , this does not make sense to the circumplanetary disk formation theories. This is not a suitable way to reduce the Q parameter value. Small mass planets are less dominant gravitationally, this means that thermal effects should be more dominant in that kind of disks. It has also been demonstrated that planets with small masses cannot maintain a circumplanetary disk around them (e.g. [Ayliffe & Bate, 2009b](#)). Therefore we do not expect that small mass planets have gravitational instabilities.

Planetary accretion is a mechanism which helps to the disk stability. In our simulation, the mass is removed from the planet location to avoid material accumulation. This mass is not added to the planet mass. In the real world, the planets accrete mass and they become bigger. As planet mass grows, its gravitational force gets stronger. This means that the gas rotates with a larger angular velocity around a more massive object. Therefore as the planet accretes, the circumplanetary disk epicyclic frequency grows and the disk becomes more stable.

5.4.3 Dependence on surface density

Following equation (5.21), a more massive disk would tend to be unstable. It has been found that CPD are more massive with increments on the viscosity ([Uribe et al., 2013](#)). Viscosity allows angular momentum transport, then material is moved radially more efficiently, supplying more material into the CPD. Our simulation does not have a prescribed viscosity. If we adopted viscosity we could expect a more massive disk. Nevertheless, this could generate a disk not more than ten times more massive, for a typical α_ν viscosity parameter ($10^{-3} - 10^{-2}$) ([Uribe et al., 2013](#)).

Another possibility could be a circumstellar disk with greater surface density. This could generate more massive circumplanetary disks. Observations have shown that circumstellar disks have

similar surface density profiles like the MNSN (Andrews et al., 2009, 2010). We cannot change drastically the circumstellar disk in order to generate more massive circumplanetary disks. We do not expect that this could be a mechanism which could generate a more massive CPD. On the other hand, denser circumstellar disks would affect significantly planetary migration due to torques.

We can observe from equations 5.5 and 5.14, that the surface density drops faster than the rotation profile of the disk, consequently, far away from the protoplanet the surface density would be weaker than dynamics.

From this qualitative analysis, we do not find any mechanism which could generate more massive disks (maybe only one order of magnitude larger). Therefore it is possible that there are not circumplanetary disk massive enough to generate gravitational instabilities.

5.4.4 Are there unstable circumplanetary disks?

Now we can estimate the existence of gravitational instabilities in circumplanetary disks based on subsections 5.4.1, 5.4.2 and 5.4.3. Realistic circumplanetary disks should be hotter than the one found in this simulation. They should have a mass of the same order of magnitude than our simulated, hence their dynamics should be similar. Therefore the Q profile shown in figure 5.18 could not get much smaller than unity (under the typical conditions discussed here).

Shabram & Boley (2013) studied briefly this topic. They simulated circumplanetary disks around a giant planet in wide orbits ($\sim 100\text{AU}$), this means colder disks than the ones in our simulations. Their more massive disk started the simulation with an initial Q parameter equal to 1.1, this is in the limit of collapse. Nevertheless, this disk finished with a minimum Q value of 1.7 at the end of their simulation. This means that the disk became stable, even when it was initiated in a quasi-unstable condition. Therefore the spiral arms observed around the CPD are due to tidal forces, not to gravitational instabilities. These tidal forces have been studied previously (e.g. Rivier et al., 2012).

Figure 5.19(a) shows the time dependence of the Q parameter for our HRAS model. At the first orbit, the Q parameter is closer to unity than at the orbit 25, which means that initially the circumplanetary disk is less stable. As long as the system evolves, the disk becomes more stable. For orbits 3 and 5, there are values of $Q < 100$ inside the disk radius. For larger orbits, the disk reaches its maximum stability ($Q > 100$), like the one shown in figure 5.18. Therefore our circumplanetary disk becomes more stable, similar to the result found by Shabram & Boley (2013). Figures 5.19(b) and (c) show the time dependence of Σ_{CPD} and κ , respectively, in order to analyze which generates this disk stabilization. Figure 5.19(c) shows that, κ maintains its initial value from orbit 1 to 25. This means that the angular velocity profiles of the circumplanetary disk is reached rapidly in the simulation. Hence the Q value does not change in time because of κ . We can see in figure 5.19(b) the changing behavior of Σ_{CPD} on time, it maintains its profile but its value decreases as the system evolves.

This Σ_{CPD} behavior is explained as follows: when the simulation started, the gravitational potential attracts material towards the planet position, this generates material accumulation. This explains the mass excess at the first orbits. As long as the system evolves, the accretion mechanism does not allow mass accumulation near the planet, since mass at the planet position is extracted from the simulation. After a few orbits, the mass excess is regulated near the planet, this allows that the circumplanetary disk also regulates its mass. At any given point the system arrives at a quasi-static equilibrium reaching its final circumplanetary disk surface density. This behavior explains the circumplanetary disk stabilization. We do not know if the disk stabilization found by Shabram & Boley (2013) is similar to the one that found here. They used radiative hydrodynamics simulations, therefore other mechanisms could modify this conclusion.

Figure 5.19: Radial profile of Q (a), Σ_{CPD} (b) and κ (c) for orbits 1 (open circles), 3 (crosses), 5 (filled squares), 10 (open squares), 15 (stars) and 25 (filled circles). Vertical dashed line represents $1/3 r_{\text{Hill}}$.

We also can compare the conditions which allow gravitational instabilities in circumstellar disks. Mayer et al. (2002) found that planets could form in circumstellar disks via gravitational collapse. They showed that Jupiter-like planets could be formed far away from the protostar in the circumstellar disk cold regions. There are two circumstellar disk properties which allow gravitational collapse: first, mass distribution in CSD has a mass profile given by $\Sigma_{\text{CSD}} \propto r^{-1.5} - r^0$. This allows that farther away from the star, mass does not drop abruptly, hence, there is a considerable amount of mass even at large radii. Second, circumstellar disks are allowed to have large extensions, of the order of thousands of AU, at these radii, they are cold enough to allow gravitational instabilities. Therefore circumstellar disks can be unstable at larger radii and from these instabilities giant planets can be formed. Circumplanetary disks do not have these properties. First, their mass distribution drops faster than in circumstellar disks ($\Sigma_{\text{CPD}} \propto r^{-2}$), therefore its mass is concentrated near the planet. We demonstrated this when we calculated the disk size, almost all the mass around the protoplanet is concentrated inside $1/3r_{\text{Hill}}$. Therefore, far away from the protoplanet there is just a small portion of mass. Second, circumplanetary disks have a small size (relative to circumstellar disks), this means that they are not large enough to have very cold exterior zones (our simulation does not allow to obtain a temperature profile, but based on Aylliffe & Bate (2009a) a temperature profile should vary as $r^{-7/10}$, getting colder at larger radii). The other alternative to get cold regions in a circumplanetary disk is that it forms around a protoplanet which is far away from the star, at several astronomical units. What happens if the CPD is formed in a planet at the outskirts of the CSD? A planet in a wide orbit r would have a sound speed c_s , smaller than a planet with a smaller orbit $r_0 < r$ with sound speed $c_{s,0}$. We can relate these two sound speeds as

$$c_s = c_{s,0} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^{-1/2}. \quad (5.27)$$

If we assume that our simulated planet has an orbit of 5AU, its wide orbit counterpart (could be $r = 100\text{AU}$) should have a sound velocity

$$c_s \approx 0.22c_{s,0}. \quad (5.28)$$

Therefore a planet at 100AU would have a CPD sound velocity just one fifth of one at 5AU (which implies a temperature of the same order of magnitude). This sound velocity value is not small enough to destabilize the disk. Hence, even if a circumplanetary disk forms around a planet with a wide orbit, it can not get cold enough to destabilize the disk.

These results show that the creation of gravitational instabilities is difficult via mass agglomeration or cold regions. These differences mark a notable breakpoint between circumstellar and circumplanetary disks. Showing that they are not physically equivalent systems. Circumplanetary disk can not be thought as mini-circumstellar disks. Therefore, moon formation in circumplanetary disks does not have to be equal to planet formation in circumstellar disks.

Fujii et al. (2014) studied the existence of the magnetorotational instability (MRI) in circumplanetary disks. They did not find a region which could sustain a well-developed MRI turbulence in the disk. They argue that if there is no angular momentum transport in the CPD (such as MRI), material should accumulate, and then the disk would become gravitationally unstable. Actually, all works have found stable disks, even researches with small viscosity simulations (e.g. Szulágyi et al., 2014). To test the scenario predicted by Fujii et al., we need two new conditions in the forthcoming simulations. First, we need simulations with higher resolution to avoid numerical viscosity, in this way, we could study systems with vanishing viscosity and in this way to analyze if the material is radially transported or not. Second, long term simulations evolving the circumstellar disks, in

this way, we could study if the material accumulates in the circumplanetary disk as long as the system evolves for hundred of orbits, and to analyze how the circumplanetary disk is affected by the circumstellar disk evolution.

We conclude that circumplanetary disks are highly stable structures (at least in the equilibrium phase of the CSDs). They are far away from the collapse due to gravitational instabilities. If unstable circumplanetary disks exist, they should be unusual under non typical conditions (such as really massive or extremely cold disks).

5.5 Implications for moon formation

Canup & Ward (2006) found that satellite systems around giant planets have a mass near to $\sim 10^{-4}$ times the host planet mass. Since moons are made principally of solids, we expect to have enough material in the circumplanetary disk to create moons. Our simulation gives a CPD mass of 3% the planet mass, which corresponds to 0.03% of dust, assuming a dust-to-gas ratio of 0.01. For a protoplanet with a Jupiter mass ($M_J = 1.9 \times 10^{30}$ g), this corresponds to a mass of 5.7×10^{28} g of gas and 5.7×10^{26} g of solids. Galilean moons have a mass of 3.9×10^{26} g (Canup & Ward, 2002). Therefore the mass contained in the disk in solid state has the same order of magnitude as the mass required to form the Galilean moons. We are not thinking that once the disk has been created, moons use all the material and they are created immediately. Canup & Ward (2006) found that when moons are forming, there are two competing forces which balances the quantity of available mass: the inflow material towards the satellites, and satellite losses due to orbital decay driven by the gas. This means that circumplanetary disks are an excellent reservoir which contains $\sim 10^{-4}$ planet masses in solids, moons could obtain mass from this source of material. While the equilibrium described by Canup & Ward (2006) maintains, circumplanetary disks are an excellent reservoir for moons formation. If this is true, giant exoplanets should have similar satellite systems with similar moons-to-planet masses ratios.

It is expected that moons form in the circumplanetary disk at the same time that the planet does (because at this time the circumplanetary disk exists). There are two alternatives: moons forms from material in the circumplanetary disk, or satellitesimals are accreted into the circumplanetary disk and later they will become moons accreting material from it.

Canup & Ward (2002) describe the basic mechanism to grow solids in a CPD: solid material (rock + ice) must be supplied either by direct transport of small amounts of material into the disk with the gas inflow, or by capture of heliocentrically orbiting solids as they pass through the disk. Particles smaller than 1m would be expected to be delivered into the accretion disk with the hydrodynamic gas inflow. Particles small enough to be captured as they pass through the disk would also be small enough to have their motion dominated by the nebular gas motion. Solids delivered into the disk with the inflowing gas would achieve an orbit around the planet at a similar orbital distance than that at which the gas achieved centrifugal balance, i.e., with $r < r_c$. Once in the circumplanetary orbit, objects large enough to decouple from the gas could collisionally aggregate on timescales much shorter than those on which they would be carried inward or outward together with the gas over a wide range of gas-to-dust values. These large objects interact with the gas through aerodynamic gas drag and also present migration. Objects would accumulate on timescales much shorter than their orbital decay time as a result of gas drag for a wide range of gas-to-solids ratios. As gas and solids are delivered into the disk, the gas sustains a quasi-steady state, while the surface density of solids will build up over time.

Tanigawa et al. (2012) presented a 3D analysis of gas and angular momentum distribution

Figure 5.20: Flow structure of the circumplanetary disk obtained from HRAS simulation at the $Y = 0$ plane. This figure is equivalent to figure 17 of [Tanigawa et al. \(2012\)](#).

in circumplanetary disks. They show a schematic picture of the fluxes around the protoplanet, including the CPD. This scheme with our simulated data is shown in figure 5.20. They argue that gas accretion towards the CPD is through vertical inflow of low density gas and grains settle in the circumstellar disk midplane, this polar inflow injects dust-poor gas into the circumplanetary disk (indicated in the figure). Farther away from the CPD size, there are gas outflows at the midplane; this also should be dust-poor gas. As long as dust is added to the circumplanetary disk, this enhances the dust-to-gas ratio in it. Once a big grain is created, it will not be taken out of the circumplanetary disk easily. As dust settles at midplane, grains are allowed to grow in there. This could start a growing grain phase, as was pointed out by [Canup & Ward \(2002\)](#).

On the other hand, [Tanigawa et al. \(2014\)](#) studied the efficiency of capturing solid material onto the circumplanetary disk from circumstellar disk material. They found that the distance from the planet to the captured particle decreases with increasing particle size. Accretion efficiency reaches its maximum when the particle has a size of $\sim 10^2 \text{m}$ (for a MMSN density and a Jupiter-like planet at 5AU). These results show that satellitetesimals can also be accreted to the circumplanetary disk from the proplyd. Once this happens, the solid body can grow through dust agglomeration inside the CPD. This process could create moons.

Our simulation is the first step in order to understand satellite formation in a circumplanetary disk. It is in agreement with previous studies about moon formation around giant planets. Our circumplanetary disk is an ideal place to form moons around a Jupiter-like planet. We found that gravitational instabilities do not play any important role in this process, since disks are very stable structures. The mass content in the circumplanetary disk agrees with the necessary mass to build up moons around giant planets, like the ones in the solar system (specially the Galilean moons around Jupiter). Our hydrodynamical simulation is able to analyze the small grains paths, as they are coupled to the gas motion. Nevertheless, we cannot conclude anything about bigger particles with this kind of simulation. To understand the role of dust dynamics in circumplanetary disks it is necessary to run simulations that include the kinematics of the dust particles coupled to the gas.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSIONS

We studied circumplanetary disk stability and its role in moon formation around giant planets. We used three-dimensional hydrodynamical simulations using the versatile `FARGO3D` code. These are the first circumplanetary disk simulations made with this code. We simulated a circumstellar disk according to the MMSN model, in order to study a Jupiter-like protoplanet around a Sun-like star.

Our model reproduces features of a circumstellar disk with an embedded protoplanet. These are: density waves perturbations and gap opening. They coincide with previous works focused on those topics. These results are encouraging with respect to the validity of our model.

Numerical effects on the simulations were analyzed. We found that planetary accretion effects are not important in order to study circumstellar disk features, such as gap formation or density waves. Circumplanetary disks are strongly affected by accretion. They can not be simulated if there is no prescribed accretion, since material accumulates around the protoplanet like a spheroidal envelope, instead of a disk-like structure. We found also that the shear sheet approximation is not a good method to obtain circumstellar disk properties, since there are numerical artifacts which modify its structure. However, circumplanetary disks are not affected by this approach, hence shear sheet approach can be used in order to speed up computational time for circumplanetary disks studies.

We characterized the circumplanetary disk formation by analyzing the 3D fluxes distribution around the protoplanet. We found that a CPD is formed around the protoplanet from material which comes from the vertical direction like polar inflows. This result cannot be obtained from 2D simulations, therefore 3D models are absolutely necessary in order to analyze circumplanetary disk physics.

We obtained circumplanetary disk properties, such as density distribution, velocity, mass, etc. All these results are in agreement with previous researches which used different numerical codes. This concordance between different works is useful to obtain real physical properties of circumplanetary disks which are independents of the numerical approach. Therefore our simulation is a good model to understand circumplanetary disk physics.

Circumplanetary disk properties are very different from those of circumstellar disks. This marks a difference between these two systems. This means that circumplanetary disks are not a small version of circumstellar disks. The dominant forces and relative scales in each system are not

scalable. This encourages the study of circumplanetary disks as a new branch of planetary formation theories. These differences should bring about discrepancies between the physical mechanisms which rule both environments, such as massive companion formation (planets in CSDs and moons in CPDs).

We solved the initial question, can moons be formed by gravitational collapses in circumplanetary disks? We found that circumplanetary disk are gravitationally stable structures in the circumstellar disk equilibrium phase. This result has several implications: moons cannot be formed from gravitational instabilities. This differentiates between planetary and satellite formation. They both are created in disks, but it seems that moons only form from grain accumulation, in contrast to planet formation (since planets can be formed from gravitational instabilities).

Our circumplanetary disk is an excellent reservoir to form satellites. It has the required mass to form the Galilean mass around a planet with a Jupiter-like mass. Our model agrees with previous works which showed that circumplanetary disks allow grain growth inside them. Although our simulation does not use dust, we can trace the small grains paths, since they are coupled to the gas motion. Our results reinforce the moon formation in circumplanetary disk model.

Perspectives

To understand better the circumplanetary disk stability, long term simulations of circumplanetary disks inside evolving circumstellar disks should be performed. In this way, the effects of changing mass fluxes towards the circumplanetary disk could be traced, and in this way obtaining the possible circumplanetary disk changes. With the aim to better understand the role of circumplanetary disks in moon formation processes, improved – theoretical or numerical – models are necessary. In order to reach this, coupled gas-dust simulations are required. In this way, grain dynamics and growth would be more precise.

There are other physical mechanism which could change the circumplanetary disk behavior: such as planetary migration or magnetic fields. For example, if a planet changes its radial position in the CSD, then its Hill radius is also modified, then this could change the circumplanetary disk properties (such as the size). Magnetic fields could change CPD dynamics, since they could generate viscosity. Magnetic fields could also allow other physical phenomena such as polar jets or planetary accretion. In order to infer the physical importance of magnetic fields in circumplanetary disks, models with and without magnetic fields should be compared with forthcoming better observations of them.

A better thermal treatment of gas and dust will help to characterize temperature profiles of grains in CPDs. In this way, observational properties could be estimated, or directly compared, with dust emission (at mid-infrared or millimetric wavelengths). Dust emission by circumplanetary disks could be observed with new technologies (e.g. *ALMA*). Thus, it would be possible to obtain physical properties directly from observations and then compare them with models.

Circumplanetary disk models –together with planetary formation theories– show that moons should be a common characteristic around giant exoplanets. This theoretical requirement is challenging for observational technologies and data reduction procedures. New observational techniques are necessary in order to detect exomoons. In this way models and observations help each other. Models encourage new observational methods, and observations demand better models. We could expect –possibly– an exomoon catalog in the incoming years, enhancing day by day the Galileo legacy.

Appendices

APPENDIX A

A fast manual to use the `fargo_tools` package

This is a brief manual to introduce `FARGO3D` code users who want to learn the use of `fargo_tools`. This package manual includes how to get the data from the hydrodynamical simulations and to visualize 3D data with the `Paraview` software. It is assumed you use some Linux distribution and you are familiarized with the terminal environment.

The text in verbatim after the `$` symbol means the commands that you need enter in the terminal. If you copy these command lines one by one you could follow this tutorial very easy. In this tutorial is assumed that you will download the `fargo_tools` and `fargo3d` in your home directory.

A.1 Downloading `fargo_tools`

The `fargo_tools` package is available on https://github.com/oscaribv/fargo_tools, there are two options to download it, you can clone the repository with `git` or you can download a `.zip` file and decompress it. Select your favorite.

A.1.1 Cloning the repository

If you are familiarized with the version control system `git` you can clone it to your computer easily. Be sure you are in your home directory and then clone it.

```
$ cd
$ git clone https://github.com/oscaribv/fargo_tools
```

This created a directory called `fargo_tools` in your home directory. The advantage on use `git` is the possibility to follow the changes to this package easily with `git pull` (learn more about `git` in <https://git-scm.com/>).

A.1.2 Download the zip file

Be sure you are in your home directory and then download the latest version of `fargo_tools`

```
$ cd
$ wget https://github.com/oscaribv/fargo_tools/archive/master.zip
```

Now you have a `master.zip` file, decompress it

```
$ unzip master.zip
```

This creates a directory called `fargo_tools_master`, renamed it to `fargo_tools` to be consistent with this tutorial

```
$ mv fargo_tools_master fargo_tools
```

If you use this method, you should download a new zip file each time a new version of `fargo_tools` is released.

Now you should have the `fargo_tools` directory in your home directory, the next step is to create some FARGO3D outputs to play with.

A.2 Creating some FARGO3D outputs

Let's start in our home directory

```
$ cd
$ pwd
/home/oscar
```

At first, you need to download the FARGO3D code from its official web page

```
$ wget http://fargo.in2p3.fr/downloads/fargo3d-1.0.tar.gz
```

the next step is to decompress it (the name can change depending on the FARGO3D version)

```
$ tar -xvf fargo3d-1.0.tar.gz
```

This will create a directory called `fargo3d-1.0` (The name can vary depending on the version). Change to the `fargo3d` directory

```
$ cd fargo3d-1.0
```

Inside this directory you can compile the `fargo3d` code if you have the correct compilers (see FARGO3D's manual, <http://fargo.in2p3.fr/manuals/html/index.html>). Let's compile the default `p3disof` setup, which is a full 3D isothermal circumstellar disk

```
$ make SETUP=p3disof para
```

```
.
.
.
```

All objects are OK. Linking stage

```
FARGO3D SUMMARY:
=====
```

This built is PARALLEL (MPI). Use "make seq" to change that

```
SETUP:      'p3disof'
(Use "make SETUP=[valid_setup_string]" to change set up)
(Use "make list" to see the list of setups implemented)
(Use "make info" to see the current sticky build options)
```

```
rm zmax_bound.c ymax_bound.c ymin_bound.c zmin_bound.c
make[1]: Leaving directory '/home/oscar/fargo3d-1.0/bin'
```

I decided to compile it to run in parallel with CPUs, but you can compile it with GPU or in the sequential slow way (again see FARGO3D manual). If the compilation does not mark an error you are ready to generate your data, if it does, you need to check your compilers.

It is time to run the simulation

```
$ mpirun -np 8 ./fargo3d -m setups/p3disof/p3disof.par
```

```
.
.
.
```

Doesn't feel the disk potential

Doesn't feel the other planets potential

```
Found 32 communicators
```

OUTPUTS 0 at date t = 0.000000 OK

```
.....TRYING TO OPEN ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
TRYING TO OPEN ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
TRYING TO OPEN ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
TRYING TO OPEN ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
```

```
TRYING TO OPEN ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
TRYING TO OPEN ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
```

```

Process 0 creates the directory ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
TRYING TO OPEN ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
TRYING TO OPEN ./outputs/p3disof//FG000000/
.....
.....
.....

```

I ran the simulation with eight processors, this can vary depending on your computer or if you are using a sequential or GPU run. The `-m` flag is quite important to use, since this generate the data in the way that `fargo_tools` needs. Wait some time until the system evolves, let's stop the simulation after 10 outputs, you can do this typing `Ctrl + C`.

```

.....
.....
OUTPUTS 10 at date t = 31.415927 OK
.....
Ctrl + C

```

Now you have finished the `FARGO3D` execution, some output files have been created. These output files are stored in `fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/`, there are a lot of types of output files, to learn more about them, read `FARGO3D` documentation.

A.3 Using t2csv

The `fargo_tools` directory contains a directory called `t2csv`, lets move there in

```
$ cd ~/fargo_tools/t2csv
```

Typing the `ls` command, you will see a `makefile` file, and if `OPENMP` is correctly installed, it should compile, then an executable file called `t2csv` and some `.o` files are created.

```

$ pwd
/home/oscar/fargo_tools/t2csv
$ ls
makefile
$ make
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store -c ../sources_f90/t2csv.f90
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store -c ../sources_f90/trans_coords.f90
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store -c ../sources_f90/create_names.f90
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store -c ../sources_f90/input_file.f90
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store t2csv.o trans_coords.o
create_names.o input_file.o -o t2csv
$ ls
create_names.o input_file.o makefile t2csv t2csv.o trans_coords.o

```

If you obtain some like that in your computer, you are ready to use `t2csv`. The next step is to copy the `t2csv` file to your output file directory, this directory must be inside `fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/`, after copy it, lets move to this directory.

```

$ cp t2csv ~/fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/
$ cd ~/fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/
$ ls
bigplanet0.dat   FG000008      gasenergy0.dat  gasvx2.dat     gasvy5.dat     gasvz8.dat
density0_2d.dat  FG000009      gasenergy10.dat gasvx3.dat     gasvy6.dat     gasvz9.dat
dimensions.dat   FG000010      gasenergy1.dat  gasvx4.dat     gasvy7.dat     grid000.inf
domain_x.dat     gasdens0.dat  gasenergy2.dat  gasvx5.dat     gasvy8.dat     grid001.inf
domain_y.dat     gasdens10.dat gasenergy3.dat  gasvx6.dat     gasvy9.dat     IDL.var
domain_z.dat     gasdens1.dat  gasenergy4.dat  gasvx7.dat     gasvz0.dat     orbit0.dat
FG000000         gasdens2.dat  gasenergy5.dat  gasvx8.dat     gasvz10.dat    planet0.dat
FG000001         gasdens3.dat  gasenergy6.dat  gasvx9.dat     gasvz1.dat     t2csv
FG000002         gasdens4.dat  gasenergy7.dat  gasvy0.dat     gasvz2.dat     torq_planet_0.dat
FG000003         gasdens5.dat  gasenergy8.dat  gasvy10.dat    gasvz3.dat     tqwk0.dat
FG000004         gasdens6.dat  gasenergy9.dat  gasvy1.dat     gasvz4.dat     variables.par
FG000005         gasdens7.dat  gasvx0.dat     gasvy2.dat     gasvz5.dat     vx0_2d.dat
FG000006         gasdens8.dat  gasvx10.dat    gasvy3.dat     gasvz6.dat     vy0_2d.dat
FG000007         gasdens9.dat  gasvx1.dat     gasvy4.dat     gasvz7.dat     vz0_2d.dat

```

Before running `t2csv`, an input file must be created, such a file must be named `input.dat`, and it has to have the next data in the following order

1. Number of cells in the X direction
2. Number of cells in the Y direction
3. Number of cells in the Z direction
4. Minimum output file to be transformed
5. Maximum output file to be transformed
6. Size of the jump between output files to be transformed
7. Min value in X direction
8. Max value in X direction
9. Min value in Y direction
10. Max value in Y direction
11. Min value in Z direction
12. Max value in Z direction
13. Grid Geometry. s for spherical, c for cylindrical, r for cartesian

If you are familiarized with the `FARGO3D` code, the values for 1-3, 7-12 can be obtained from the `.par` file, the value for 13 is obtained from the `.opt` file and the values for 4-6 are defined by the user. You can fill the `input.dat` file according to your simulation. For the `p3disof` setup, open a file called `input.dat` with your favorite text editor and fill it with the next lines

```

100      #Number of cells in the X direction
80       #Number of cells in the Y direction
40       #Number of cells in the Z direction
0        #minimum output file to be transformed
10       #maximum output file to be transformed
1        #size of the jump between output files to be transformed
-3.14159 #Min value in X direction
3.14159  #Max value in X direction
0.6      #Min value in Y direction
1.5      #Max value in Y direction
1.42     #Min value in Z direction
1.72     #Max value in Z direction
s        #s for spherical, c for cylindrical, r for cartesian

```

That means that our grid is 100, 80 and 40 cells in the X, Y, Z coordinate, respectively. We want to transform the output files from the 0 to the 10 output, one by one (it means that the output files from 0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 will be used, if we would want 0,2,4,6,8,10 we had specified 2 in the size of the jump, and so on). The domain of our grid goes from $[-\pi : \pi]$ in azimuth, $[0.6 : 1.5]$ in radius and $[1.42 : 1.72]$ in colatitude. The grid geometry is spherical so the s character is used. Now the input.dat file must be in the same directory as t2csv

```

$ ls
bigplanet0.dat  FG000009      gasenergy1.dat  gasvx5.dat    gasvy9.dat    input.dat
density0_2d.dat FG000010      gasenergy2.dat  gasvx6.dat    gasvz0.dat    orbit0.dat
dimensions.dat  gasdens0.dat  gasenergy3.dat  gasvx7.dat    gasvz10.dat   planet0.dat
domain_x.dat   gasdens10.dat gasenergy4.dat  gasvx8.dat    gasvz1.dat    t2csv
domain_y.dat   gasdens1.dat  gasenergy5.dat  gasvx9.dat    gasvz2.dat    torq_planet_0.dat
domain_z.dat   gasdens2.dat  gasenergy6.dat  gasvy0.dat    gasvz3.dat    tqwk0.dat
FG000000       gasdens3.dat  gasenergy7.dat  gasvy10.dat   gasvz4.dat    variables.par
FG000001       gasdens4.dat  gasenergy8.dat  gasvy1.dat    gasvz5.dat    vx0_2d.dat
FG000002       gasdens5.dat  gasenergy9.dat  gasvy2.dat    gasvz6.dat    vy0_2d.dat
FG000003       gasdens6.dat  gasvx0.dat      gasvy3.dat    gasvz7.dat    vz0_2d.dat
FG000004       gasdens7.dat  gasvx10.dat     gasvy4.dat    gasvz8.dat
FG000005       gasdens8.dat  gasvx1.dat      gasvy5.dat    gasvz9.dat
FG000006       gasdens9.dat  gasvx2.dat      gasvy6.dat    grid000.inf
FG000007       gasenergy0.dat gasvx3.dat      gasvy7.dat    grid001.inf
FG000008       gasenergy10.dat gasvx4.dat      gasvy8.dat    IDL.var

```

Now t2csv can be executed

```

$ mpirun -np 4 ./t2csv
Creating disk      0 .csv file by processor      1
Creating disk      1 .csv file by processor      2
Creating disk      3 .csv file by processor      4
Creating disk      2 .csv file by processor      3
Creating disk      6 .csv file by processor      3
Creating disk      5 .csv file by processor      2
Creating disk      4 .csv file by processor      1
Creating disk      7 .csv file by processor      4

```

```

Creating disk          10 .csv file by processor          3
Creating disk          9 .csv file by processor          2
Creating disk          8 .csv file by processor          1
The csv files have been created inside csv_files directory

```

If you obtain a similar output, it means a new directory called `csv_files` has been created. This new directory contains the `disk m .csv` files. You should obtain some like this

```

$ cd csv_files
$ ls
disk0.csv  disk1.csv  disk3.csv  disk5.csv  disk7.csv  disk9.csv
disk10.csv disk2.csv  disk4.csv  disk6.csv  disk8.csv
$ head disk10.csv
X, Y, Z, lden, vx, vy, vz, lenergy
-0.59319105770894343      , -1.5740857362501043E-006 , 9.0135281947011495E-002 ,
-4.8342743671298392      , 1.0866022838070270E-006 , -0.40948389480738567      ,
0.00000000000000000000    , -1.3010299956639813
-0.59199667437804870      , -3.7624041166033385E-002 , 9.0135281947011495E-002 ,
-4.8342743696691226      , 2.5972136210949341E-002 , -0.40865940464833644      ,
0.00000000000000000000    , -1.3010299956639813
.
.
.

```

The X, Y, Z columns correspond to the rectangular coordinates, `lden` and `lenergy` to the base 10 logarithm of density and energy, respectively and `vx`, `vy`, `vz` to the velocity components in rectangular coordinates. These files can be used to visualize the data.

A.4 Visualizing 3D data with Paraview

In general, csv files can be opened with several programs with different purposes, in this work it is shown how to visualize 3D-data with Paraview (<http://www.paraview.org/>). Once you have installed it, you can open it from the terminal (you must be in your `csv_files` directory)

```

$ pwd
/home/oscar/fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/csv_files
$ paraview &

```

The visual version of Paraview will start. To understand better how to visualize the data, follow the next steps following figures [A.1](#), [A.2](#), [A.3](#), [A.4](#), [A.5](#), [A.6](#) and the numbers labeled there in.

1. Open the file manager clicking on the button marked in figure [A.1](#).
2. Select the file `disk10.csv` and click on the “ok” button.
3. When the file is opened, it appears in the pipeline browser, select it as is shown in figure [A.2](#).
4. Click on the apply button, and the csv file will be displayed as a table (see figure [A.2](#)).
5. The next step converts the data into a grid form. Click on the Filters button and search for Table to Structured Grid.

6. Now it appears a new attribute in the pipeline browser called TableToStructuredGrid1, select it (see Fig. A.3).
7. You need to fill correctly the Whole Extent section and the X, Y, Z columns. The Whole extent must coincide with the original grid dimension. Remember the simulation is 100, 80, 40 cells in X, Y, Z. Then we fill the Whole Extent section with these values (see figure A.3). The X, Y, Z columns must coincide with the csv columns labeled as X, Y, Z (see figure A.3). When this is done, click on the apply button, now the data is displayed as seen in figure A.3.
8. Click on the + button to create another layout to visualize the data.
9. Click on the eye shape symbol (see figure A.4) and you will see the outline grid visualization as the one showed in figure A.4.
10. To visualize a field data, change outline to surface view (see A.5).
11. Select lden to visualize the density logarithm data, you should obtain something like figure A.5.
12. To finish, let's make a cut on the grid to visualize the density profile. Select the cut icon (see Fig. A.6).
13. Select a cut normal to Y.
14. Press apply, you should obtain something like in the figure A.6. This is the typical 3D-density profile of an isothermal circumstellar disk.

Now you can manipulate a circumstellar disk with your own hands! These are the basics for Paraview visualization. A lot of amazing things you can do using the csv files and this software. To learn more about Paraview capabilities, read the online documentation in http://www.paraview.org/Wiki/The_ParaView_Tutorial.

Another powerful characteristic of Paraview, is that allows to create python scripts to analyze multiple files. This is very useful in analyzing FARGO3D data. To learn more about to this check http://www.paraview.org/Wiki/ParaView/Python_Scripting.

A.5 Using extractor

Let's point out a problem to show the possible application of the `extractor` tool. We have already simulated a 3D disk with low resolution, as the one shown in §A.2. If we simulate it with high resolution, the output files of the FARGO3D code would use a lot of hard disk space. We would like to use `t2csv` directly on these files, but the problem is worst that just a possible HD saturation. If we would try to visualize this large csv files with paraview, the RAM consumption could be a great problem, and the analysis of the data is practically impossible. On the other hand, we just want to analyze the data around the protoplanet, we only need to study that section of the grid, what can we do? The solution is to use the `extractor` tool to obtain smaller binary files – only the part of the grid to study – and then transform them using `2csv`.

Compilation of `extractor` is in the same way that for `t2csv`. The `fargo_tools` root contains a directory called `extractor`, let's move there in

```
$ cd ~/fargo_tools/extractor
```


Figure A.1: 3D visualization with Paraview. Steps 1-2.

Figure A.2: 3D visualization with Paraview. Steps 3-5.

Figure A.3: 3D visualization with Paraview. Steps 6-8.

Figure A.4: 3D visualization with Paraview. Step 9.

Figure A.5: 3D visualization with Paraview. Steps 10-11.

Figure A.6: 3D visualization with Paraview. Steps 12-14.

Typing the `ls` command, you will see a `makefile` file, and if `OPENMP` is correctly installed, it should compile, then an executable file called `extracter` and some `.o` files are created.

```
$ pwd
/home/oscar/fargo_tools/extracter
$ ls
makefile
$ make
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store -c ../sources_f90/extracter.f90
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store -c ../sources_f90/trans_coords.f90
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store -c ../sources_f90/create_names.f90
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store -c ../sources_f90/input_file.f90
mpif90 -cpp -finit-local-zero -fno-automatic -ffloat-store extracter.o trans_coords.o
create_names.o input_file.o -o extracter
$ ls
create_names.o extracter extracter.o input_file.o makefile trans_coords.o
```

If you obtain some like that in your computer, you are ready to use `extracter`. The next step is to copy the `extracter` file to your output file directory, this directory must be inside `fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/`, after copy it, let's move to this directory.

```
$ cp extracter ~/fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/
$ cd ~/fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/
$ ls
bigplanet0.dat    FG000008      gasenergy0.dat  gasvx2.dat     gasvy5.dat     gasvz8.dat
density0_2d.dat  FG000009      gasenergy10.dat gasvx3.dat     gasvy6.dat     gasvz9.dat
dimensions.dat   FG000010      gasenergy1.dat  gasvx4.dat     gasvy7.dat     grid000.inf
domain_x.dat     gasdens0.dat  gasenergy2.dat  gasvx5.dat     gasvy8.dat     grid001.inf
domain_y.dat     gasdens10.dat gasenergy3.dat  gasvx6.dat     gasvy9.dat     IDL.var
domain_z.dat     gasdens1.dat  gasenergy4.dat  gasvx7.dat     gasvz0.dat     orbit0.dat
FG000000         gasdens2.dat  gasenergy5.dat  gasvx8.dat     gasvz10.dat    planet0.dat
FG000001         gasdens3.dat  gasenergy6.dat  gasvx9.dat     gasvz1.dat     extracter
FG000002         gasdens4.dat  gasenergy7.dat  gasvy0.dat     gasvz2.dat     torq_planet_0.dat
FG000003         gasdens5.dat  gasenergy8.dat  gasvy10.dat    gasvz3.dat     tqwk0.dat
FG000004         gasdens6.dat  gasenergy9.dat  gasvy1.dat     gasvz4.dat     variables.par
FG000005         gasdens7.dat  gasvx0.dat     gasvy2.dat     gasvz5.dat     vx0_2d.dat
FG000006         gasdens8.dat  gasvx10.dat    gasvy3.dat     gasvz6.dat     vy0_2d.dat
FG000007         gasdens9.dat  gasvx1.dat     gasvy4.dat     gasvz7.dat     vz0_2d.dat
```

As for `t2csv`, we need to create an input file called `input_ext.dat` to be read by the program. It has the same structure than `input.dat`, the only difference is that we need to add the range that we want to extract from the arrays.

Our array in the X coordinate – azimuth for the simulation in §A.2 – has a size $NX = 100$ in the range $\phi \in [-\pi, \pi]$; the planet is at $\phi = 0$ which corresponds to $NX_i = 50$. Since we are only interested in material around the protoplanet, the range that we are interested of the array is $NX_i = [40 - 60]$, this means just 20 grid points around the protoplanet in the X coordinate. A similar analysis for the other coordinates has to be made, and a good selection of ranges in Y and Z could be $NY_i = 30 - 50$ and $NZ_i = 10 - 30$ (Since the total range on Y and Z are 80 and 40, respectively, and the planet is located at $NY_i = 40$ and $NZ_i = 20$).

At this point we know the ranges of the arrays from which we want to extract the data, the next step is to fill the `input_ext.dat`. It follows the same logic that for the `input.dat` file which is read by `t2csv`, the first twelve rows are filled equal to the `input.dat` in §A.3. The next six rows are filled with the ranges in the order: NX_{\min} , NX_{\max} , NY_{\min} , NY_{\max} , NZ_{\min} and NZ_{\max} ; the last row correspond to the geometry (s for spherical, c for cylindrical, r for cartesian). Then the `input_ext.dat` should look as

```
100      #Number of cells in the X direction
80       #Number of cells in the Y direction
40       #Number of cells in the Z direction
0        #minimum output file to be transformed
10       #maximum output file to be transformed
1        #size of the jump between output files to be transformed
-3.14159 #Min value in X direction
3.14159  #Max value in X direction
0.6      #Min value in Y direction
1.5      #Max value in Y direction
1.42     #Min value in Z direction
1.72     #Max value in Z direction
40       #NXmin
60       #NXmax
30       #NYmin
50       #NYmax
10       #NZmin
30       #NZmax
s        #s for spherical, c for cylindrical, r for cartesian
```

Once you have created the `input_ext.dat` with those lines, you are ready to run `extracter`. Run it in parallel mode using `mpirun`

```
$ mpirun -np 4 ./extracter
Transforming output =          0 in processor          1
Transforming output =          1 in processor          2
Transforming output =          2 in processor          3
Transforming output =          3 in processor          4
Transforming output =          4 in processor          1
Transforming output =          5 in processor          2
Transforming output =          6 in processor          3
Transforming output =          7 in processor          4
Transforming output =          8 in processor          1
Transforming output =          9 in processor          2
Transforming output =         10 in processor          3
The new (smaller) binary files have been created inside extractor_files directory
```

The program prints the new directory of the new binary files, in this case is `extracter_files`. Let's move there in and see the files there in

```
$ cd extractor_files
$ ls
```

```

gasdens0.dat  gasdens7.dat  gasenergy4.dat  gasvx1.dat  gasvx9.dat  gasvy6.dat  gasvz3.dat
gasdens10.dat gasdens8.dat  gasenergy5.dat  gasvx2.dat  gasvy0.dat  gasvy7.dat  gasvz4.dat
gasdens1.dat  gasdens9.dat  gasenergy6.dat  gasvx3.dat  gasvy10.dat gasvy8.dat  gasvz5.dat
gasdens2.dat  gasenergy0.dat gasenergy7.dat  gasvx4.dat  gasvy1.dat  gasvy9.dat  gasvz6.dat
gasdens3.dat  gasenergy10.dat gasenergy8.dat  gasvx5.dat  gasvy2.dat  gasvz0.dat  gasvz7.dat
gasdens4.dat  gasenergy1.dat  gasenergy9.dat  gasvx6.dat  gasvy3.dat  gasvz10.dat gasvz8.dat
gasdens5.dat  gasenergy2.dat  gasvx0.dat      gasvx7.dat  gasvy4.dat  gasvz1.dat  gasvz9.dat
gasdens6.dat  gasenergy3.dat  gasvx10.dat     gasvx8.dat  gasvy5.dat  gasvz2.dat  input.dat

```

We can see that there are similar files to the ones created by FARGO3D , but in this case they are much smaller. The original files have a size of $NX \times NY \times NZ = 100 \times 80 \times 40 = 3.2 \times 10^5$ cells for file.

We can see there is also a file called `input.dat` (this file can be used for `t2csv`, you do not have to worry to fill a new input file again!), let's see what is inside that file

```

$ head -n 13 input.dat
21      !NX
21      !NY
21      !NZ
0       !itermin
10      !itertot
1       !iterjump
-0.666397691 !X min
0.602931619 !X max
0.930379748 !R min
1.15822780 !R max
1.48923075 !Z min
1.64307690 !Z max
s       !type of plot

```

This file contains the sizes of the new arrays, which is given by $NX \times NY \times NZ = 21 \times 21 \times 21 = 9261$ cells with their respective new grid size in each coordinate. This is the real application of the `extracter` tool, we can extract the region to study of really big arrays, making the analysis really faster. If you have a super computer, this tool is not useful for you.

We are ready to use `t2csv` to visualize our smaller arrays. Let's copy it to our actual directory, which should be `extracter_files`.

```

$ pwd
/home/oscar/fargo3d-1.0/outputs/p3disof/extracter_files
$ cp ~/fargo_tools/t2csv/t2csv .

```

Actually we already have an `input.dat` file (it was created by `extracter`), then we just have to run it as in [§A.3](#)

```

$ mpirun -np 4 ./t2csv

```

```

.
.
.

```

The csv files have been created inside `csv_files` directory

Figure A.7: 3D visualization of the extracted part of the circumstellar disk with the `extracter` tool.

There is a new directory called `csv_files`, let's move there in and we will see the `diskm.csv` files. Follow the steps in A.4 to visualize the new data in paraview (take care with the new sizes of the arrays!, $X=21$, $Y=21$, $Z=21$ instead of $X=100$, $Y=80$, $Z=40$). Instead of a complete disk, you should obtain just the extracted part of the disk, as in figure A.7.

Figure A.7 is not the best example for a real use of the `extracter` tool, but this is a practical example on how to use it. Believe me, when you are dealing with really high resolution simulation, you will learn to love this tool.

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